

APPENDIX

INTERVIEW DATA RESULTS

Sports Participation, Physical Fitness, Psychosocial Well-Being,
and Challenges in Sports Programs for Students with Intellectual Disabilities

SECTION A: TEACHER INTERVIEWS

TEACHER – DHEA PUTRI DEFIYANTI

Q1: *How long have you been involved in supervising or teaching the sports program at this school?*

Answer: I started working at SLB (Special School) in 2014. Previously I was at SLB 2 Lubuk Buaya, and now at SLB 1 Negeri Padang. In total, across both schools, approximately 10 years.

Q2: *What is your main role in running the sports program?*

Answer: My role here is as a physical education teacher, supervisor, and coach. At SLB, students — particularly certain ones — are grouped together to participate in competitions held each year. My fellow teachers and I select children we believe are capable of competing, similar to how selection works in regular schools. First we look at their physical condition and health, then how well they respond to instructions, since students with intellectual disabilities (tunagrahita) typically have IQs below 90.

Q3: *How do you observe the level of student involvement in sports activities?*

Answer: I teach PE for 2 hours to mixed SMP and SMA classes — they are not separated by disability type because of the timetable. At SLB, we focus more on skills. In a week, students do sports 2 days. Combining tunagrahita and tunarungu (hearing-impaired) students is generally manageable, but including students with autism who have high tantrum levels makes it more challenging, as autism and intellectual disability often call for opposite approaches.

Q4: *What things typically influence students' enthusiasm and decision to participate?*

Answer: Children with tunagrahita need motivation. I tell them, 'If you win, if you keep trying, what do you want? I'll take you there.' Some students — especially the male students with a mix of tunalaras (behavioral disorder) — need a firmer approach. I apply firm but constructive discipline to encourage them.

Q5: *What strategies do you use to ensure all students are actively involved?*

Answer: Unlike teachers in regular schools, we cannot simply give instructions and expect students to follow. We have to get involved ourselves. If students with severe intellectual disability (C1 level) are running a zigzag route, I run along with each one of them. If I only demonstrate without joining in, they'll just stand still. When the teacher holds their hand or runs alongside, they become happy and energized.

Q6: *Do you see differences in participation interest across different types of disabilities?*

Answer: It depends not on the type of disability, but on each child's mood. Some tunagrahita students also have low-motivation days, as do tunarungu students. At SLB, I've learned that we must adapt to what the child wants — not what we want.

Q7: *How do other students react when they see their peers actively participating in sports?*

Answer: The social spirit and willingness to help here is extraordinary. For example, I once took the students on a long walk, and there was a student with tunadaksa (physical disability) whose gait was impaired. The other students — including those with tunagrahita — took turns holding and supporting him, cheering him on, even wiping his drool. Their solidarity toward their friends is remarkable.

Q8: *After students participate in the sports program, do you see improvements in their physical abilities?*

Answer: Yes. For example, there's Fajri — he was lazy at first. With some training programs and lots of motivation, he eventually won first place in the long jump competition at WNP. Progress is evident, especially when we plant enthusiasm in them. Fajri's physique looks almost like a typical person, though communication with him is like talking to a primary school child even though he's in senior high school.

Q9: *What types of adaptations do you provide to students to match their conditions?*

Answer: I group students by ability. A C (mild) tunagrahita student is not placed in the same group as a C1 (severe) student because the gap is very large. C1 students can only participate in certain sports like bocce, which requires only minimal hand-eye coordination and doesn't need extra physical strength. Grouping is essential — C and tunarungu students can be combined, but C1 and autism must be separated.

Q10: *Are there any modified game rules to facilitate students' limitations?*

Answer: Bocce, for instance, is already a sport specifically designed for children with Down Syndrome — it's part of the Paralympics and has been modified by SOINA (Special Olympics Indonesia). It's a small-ball sport similar to a modified bowling game.

Q11: *How effective are the adapted sports tools?*

Answer: Here we use regular equipment — standard balls: basketball, volleyball, football. Since we don't have students with visual impairment (tunanetra), we don't need special sound-emitting balls. The school has a sports budget every semester to equip us with standard sports gear.

Q12: *How does the sports program help increase students' self-confidence?*

Answer: Very significantly. Fajri is a great example. Before I came, there was no PE teacher here for two years. He used to be labelled as difficult. The older teachers — mostly in their 50s — had run out of energy dealing with him. I tried a firm approach after consulting with colleagues. After he won the competition, his confidence soared. He started participating in flag ceremonies, something he had never done before. Now he keeps asking, 'When's the next competition?'

Q13: *How do you describe the social interaction between disabled students and non-disabled peers?*

Answer: Looking at social media, it seems tunagrahita students with mild impairment do have friends outside school and are active on social media. Those with severe impairment (C1) may have a harder time. Fajri likes to fantasize — between exercises he'll tell me stories that are beyond reality, and I just go along with it. I relate to students like a friend, so they feel comfortable.

Q14: *Is the sports program sufficient to create an inclusive school environment?*

Answer: Yes, very much so. The socialization among students here — whether tunagrahita, tunarungu, or tunadaksa — is excellent. Their sense of social solidarity surpasses what we see in typical schools. For example, at the canteen, students who don't have parental support are helped by more capable peers. That's one reason I stay at this school.

Q15: *What are the main challenges you face in running an inclusive sports program?*

Answer: The biggest challenge for me personally is with autistic students. I don't have a background in special education (PLB), so when they have tantrums — hitting, throwing things — I'm at a loss. That's a personal limitation I need to address.

Q16: *Are school resources and facilities sufficient?*

Answer: Very much so. We have a budget every semester — not only for sports but for all programs. The school has complete facilities: fashion, culinary arts, beauty, music with a full band. Compared to vocational schools (SMK), SLB's facilities are often superior in terms of completeness.

Q17: *What support do you see from the school, parents, and community?*

Answer: The school is very supportive — whenever there's a competition, I'm immediately called to coordinate and select students, and the school provides transport and meals. Parents are also very enthusiastic; some even come to me asking to include their child. We try to be fair but also realistic about readiness. Parents here are incredible — they wait from morning to afternoon every day for their children.

Q18: *What is the main strength of the sports program?*

Answer: First, facilities. Compared to private SLBs, as a public school (SLB Negeri) we are well-funded. The school has everything including a dormitory. Teachers don't have to worry about finding space or modifying equipment. The complete facilities are the greatest support.

Q19: *What still needs to be developed or improved?*

Answer: I wish we could identify talent earlier — ideally at the elementary school (SD) level. Now we're only selecting from SMP (junior high), which is already an in-between age for sports competitions that have age categories. Starting the selection process at SD would yield better results.

Q20: *Are you confident the sports program will continue in the future?*

Answer: Very confident. With organizations like PERNAS, SOINA, and Special Olympics, talented children will keep advancing. There are 3 competitions per year at various levels — city, provincial, and national — including SOINA, ODSN, and Paralympic selection events. The school facilitates everything: transport, meals, and all logistics.

TEACHER – FITRIANI

Q1: *How long have you been involved in the sports program at this school?*

Answer: At SLB, sports classes taught by a dedicated PE teacher are provided at the SMP and SMA levels. At the SD level, homeroom teachers take responsibility for all subjects including PE. I have been a teacher since 2000 — almost 26 years.

Q2: *What is your main role in running the sports program?*

Answer: My main role is as mentor, companion, and coach. Students with intellectual disabilities cannot be pushed academically, so we focus on how they can excel through non-academic channels. Sports is one of the most effective outlets for them.

Q3: *How do you assess students' level of involvement in sports activities?*

Answer: These students are generally enthusiastic and talented in sports. When challenged with a competition, they become very serious in training. Parents are equally supportive — they stand by, ready to accompany their children to competitions at the venue.

Q4: *What influences students' enthusiasm and decision to participate?*

Answer: Three main factors: 1) the student's own ability in sports, 2) parental support, and 3) how mentoring is provided by the coach. The availability of equipment like rackets and balls for training also plays a role.

Q5: *What strategies do you use to ensure active participation from all students?*

Answer: We must observe each child's emotional state carefully. We cannot force them. If they are not in the mood, we need to read that signal and give them space. Inclusion means embracing what the child needs, not what we as teachers want to impose.

Q6: *Do you see differences in interest across different types of disabilities?*

Answer: It depends more on individual personality and ability than on type of disability. Among tunagrahita students there are those capable of academic learning (*mampu didik*) and those better suited for vocational training (*mampu latihan*). Both can excel in sports depending on individual potential.

Q7: *How do other students react when a student actively participates in sports?*

Answer: They are very supportive. When a student wins a competition, their name is announced at the Monday flag ceremony with the award presented publicly in front of all students. This motivates others who then also want to be selected and recognized.

Q8: *Do you see physical improvement after students participate in sports programs?*

Answer: Yes. Students who actively engage in Thursday morning physical exercises show notable improvement in their fitness compared to those who merely show up. Regular physical activity builds their stamina and strength.

Q9: *What adaptations are provided in physical training?*

Answer: At our school, we use regular sports equipment. Modification is mainly applied in cases of tunarungu (hearing impairment), where tools like sound-emitting ping-pong balls are used. For tunagrahita students, no special tool modification is typically required.

Q10: *How does sports affect students' confidence and psychosocial well-being?*

Answer: The impact is very clear. One tunarungu student who previously refused to socialize or make friends gradually opened up after winning a competition. Her confidence improved, she started making friends, and she became more motivated in other aspects of life as well.

Q11: *How does social interaction between disabled and non-disabled students look?*

Answer: Through sports activities in the field, social interaction becomes natural. Students from different schools and backgrounds meet and form connections. What starts as unfamiliar gradually becomes a bond — they even form 'groups' of friends.

Q12: *What are the main challenges in implementing an inclusive sports program?*

Answer: The main challenge is the technical knowledge gap. As teachers with a general education background — not specialized sports training — we need to constantly learn the correct techniques for each sport. We fear teaching incorrect techniques to our students.

Q13: *Are the school's facilities and resources adequate?*

Answer: They still need improvement. After a recent renovation, the sports hall equipment was damaged or lost, and we haven't fully replaced it. The bocce court at the back is permanent, but other facilities still need upgrading.

Q14: *What is the main strength of the sports program?*

Answer: The most important strength is the teachers' spirit and dedication. If teachers are motivated, they can motivate students. We also need to continuously improve teacher knowledge about specific sports for children with special needs.

Q15: *What needs to be developed or improved?*

Answer: Two key areas: 1) improving teacher competence through training and socialization in adapted sports, and 2) improving school facilities and sports equipment.

Q16: *Will the sports program continue in the future?*

Answer: Definitely, because it's part of the formal school curriculum (mata pelajaran olahraga). There are also structured weekly sports activities every Thursday, with students assigned to specific sports branches. The program is systematically planned and evaluated.

TEACHER – GEMI SAPUTRI

Q1: *How long have you been involved in the sports program at this school?*

Answer: My name is Gemi Saputri, homeroom teacher for Grade 8 at SMPLB Tunagrahita. I have been teaching for 17 years. I received my government appointment (SK) 2.5 years ago at this SLB Negeri. Before that I was at a private school where I also handled PE as the homeroom teacher. At SLB Negeri, we now have a PE teacher, Bu Dea, and homeroom teachers collaborate with her for sports instruction.

Q2: *Have you ever trained students and accompanied them to competitions?*

Answer: Yes, including at championship level.

Q3: *How do you assess students' involvement in sports activities?*

Answer: Children with disabilities tend to prefer physical activities over sitting at a desk. They genuinely enjoy sports. If there's even one day without sports, they get restless. The PE teacher is great with the children, so they are very active and engaged.

Q4: *What influences students' willingness to participate?*

Answer: First, the child's intrinsic interest. Second, encouragement from teachers — homeroom teachers and PE teachers — who create appeal so students feel motivated and confident enough to join competitions.

Q5: *What strategies are used to ensure all students participate?*

Answer: First, we observe what sport each child enjoys. Not all children can play all sports — it depends on their individual talent and interest. A child may have interest but not talent, or talent but not interest. Both must align, and we guide them accordingly.

Q6: *Are there differences in participation interest between different types of disabilities?*

Answer: Sports competitions at SLB are adapted to the type of disability. For intellectual disabilities, specific sports like athletics are designated. For hearing-impaired (tunarungu) students, different sports apply. The competition needs determine the sport assigned, not just personal interest.

Q7: *How do other students respond when a peer wins or achieves in sports?*

Answer: Other students become excited and motivated too — 'I want to join competitions like my senior, I want to win prizes too.' Teachers also give rewards, which further motivates the whole group.

Q8: *Do you observe physical improvements in students after joining sports activities?*

Answer: Yes. Students with intellectual disabilities can also have physical challenges — some used to trip and fall easily. After physical training, they become stronger, more stable, and can run with confidence.

Q9: *How do you measure physical improvement?*

Answer: Primarily through observation. We watch their daily movement, posture, and physical endurance over time.

Q10: *What forms of adaptation are provided during sports training?*

Answer: For students with weak physical fitness, we consult with the PE teacher to tailor the activities. For example, a student who cannot run well will receive modified exercises suited to their physical capacity.

Q11: *Are game rules modified to accommodate students' disabilities?*

Answer: Yes, rules must be modified. Modification in sports at SLB is not only acceptable — it's essential and proven effective in facilitating students' participation.

Q12: *How does sports affect students' self-confidence?*

Answer: Sports has a strong influence on self-confidence. Students who were once afraid to perform in front of others become inspired when they see their peers do it. When a teacher says 'jump forward' and the student jumps, they feel 'I can do this too.' Sport triggers a sense of achievement that builds confidence.

Q13: *How is social interaction between disabled and non-disabled students?*

Answer: When students from our class attend competitions alongside students from regular schools, their social skills also improve. They become more communicative, asking other participants about their events — things they wouldn't do normally.

Q14: *Has the sports program created an inclusive environment?*

Answer: At SLB, the students mix across different disability types, which already creates a natural form of inclusion. External inclusive monitoring is usually handled by school leadership (vice principals and assessment teams).

Q15: *What are the main challenges in running sports programs?*

Answer: Every child has different challenges. In one class of five students, there are five different problems. Some parents do not align with teachers, believing their child should not be pushed. Also, having only one PE teacher for all SMP and SMA students is very challenging, though the PE teacher's enthusiasm makes it feel manageable.

Q16: *Are facilities adequate?*

Answer: Not yet fully. The school tries to provide equipment like balance boards, but there aren't enough for all students. Teachers from different classes sometimes compete for shared resources.

Q17: *What support do parents and community provide?*

Answer: Many families have limited financial means. Some parents do provide support — sometimes they offer to drive their children or accompany them. It really depends on each family's individual situation.

Q18: *What is the main strength of the sports program?*

Answer: The students themselves — many are genuinely talented. And the teachers are willing to facilitate even without complete facilities. For example, when there's no available field, we borrow a court next door or use the nearby UNP (Universitas Negeri Padang) facilities.

Q19: *Will the program continue?*

Answer: It definitely will, because competitions are held annually and students with athletic interest and talent must continue to be developed. My hope is for better sports facilities and stronger collaboration with the sports department (Dinas Olahraga), with coaches from the agency visiting to guide technique-specific training.

TEACHER – GILANG DWI NANDA

Q1: *How long have you been involved in the sports program at this school?*

Answer: My name is Gilang Dwi Nanda. I am an arts teacher at SLBN 1 Padang, but we also have extracurricular programs for developing students' interests in sports. I have taught here for approximately 12 years. I am also an administrator of SOINA (Special Olympics Indonesia) outside of school.

Q2: *What is your main role in the sports program?*

Answer: There is already a dedicated PE teacher for technical training. The other teachers, including myself, mainly monitor the students' training progress. Since the PE teacher is alone, all of us pitch in. We're taught basic techniques and competition rules which we practice with students during their training sessions.

Q3: *How do you assess students' involvement in sports?*

Answer: For students with intellectual disabilities, their kinesthetic ability is what needs to be developed most. They are generally enthusiastic about sports — it's one of the best ways to develop their gross motor skills.

Q4: *What influences students' enthusiasm to join activities?*

Answer: First, they are drawn to sports they see and like. Second, the PE teacher makes classes fun from the beginning — using game-based media so that sports doesn't feel monotonous. For bocce athletes, for instance, there's always variation to keep them motivated. In short: variety in teaching and effective teacher-student approach are key.

Q5: *What strategies do you use to engage all students?*

Answer: Learning through play. I look for trending creative activities — even viral things on TikTok — and try them with students. Sports doesn't always have to be about competition. We aim to make physical activity a fun routine, not just a path to medals.

Q6: *Are there differences in interest between different types of disabilities?*

Answer: Yes. Children with Down Syndrome tend to enjoy bocce — it matches their abilities. They also enjoy swimming because they love water. Children with autism tend to do less well in team sports due to social challenges.

Q7: *How do other students respond to a peer's sports achievement?*

Answer: Every student who wins a competition receives their award again during the Monday flag ceremony, along with a certificate from the school. This recognition motivates other students to also want their name called during assembly.

Q8: *Do you observe physical improvements in students after sports participation?*

Answer: Yes. One student, Audia (who has since passed away due to an accident), showed remarkable physical improvement through regular swimming therapy. Swimming reduced her health risks and improved her condition significantly over time.

Q9: *How do you assess physical improvement?*

Answer: Previously, some students who appeared sleepy or unfocused were actually just physically unfit. After regular sports, their endurance and stamina improved, their focus increased, and they were more willing to participate in group activities like gotong royong (communal work).

Q10: *What adaptations are provided during training?*

Answer: Curriculum adaptations are standard practice for special needs students. For tunarungu students, visual cues replace verbal signals. For tunagrahita students, we simplify content and delivery. For wheelchair users, we modify running activities to wheelchair racing.

Q11: *How effective are these adaptations?*

Answer: Sometimes very effective, sometimes less so. But adaptations always have an impact — even if small. The key is never applying methods designed for typical children to students with special needs, as it simply won't work.

Q12: *How does sports help build students' self-confidence?*

Answer: Khalid is a good example. He transferred from a regular school where he was frequently bullied for being a slow learner. He started bullying others in return. When assessed, he was found to have both behavioral and intellectual challenges. He enrolled here unwillingly at first. But when swimming was identified as his strength, he was entered in a competition and won. From that point, his self-confidence in school transformed completely.

Q13: *How is social interaction between disabled and non-disabled students?*

Answer: For Khalid — who has mild intellectual disability — people outside wouldn't even know he has a disability. He reads, counts, and socializes well now. When we went to provide disaster relief, people were surprised to see him — 'He's from SLB?' They couldn't believe it.

Q14: *What are the main challenges?*

Answer: First, limited number of teachers — all must be mobilized for extracurricular supervision. Second, inadequate facilities: no dedicated bocce court (we converted a back area); no proper running track (we take students to UNP or UNAN). Budget is also a constraint — quality sports development requires sustained funding.

Q15: *What support do parents and community provide?*

Answer: It varies. Audia's parents were very supportive — they enrolled her in a swimming club, and she became a champion. Khalid's parents, despite being advised to do the same, did not follow through due to different priorities or mindset. About 5% of parents accompany students to competitions.

Q16: *What is the main strength of the sports program?*

Answer: We now have a dedicated PE teacher — this is a major improvement. We also have a solid team (Timwok) and flexible collaboration culture among teachers. School leadership also supports us financially as much as possible, especially for competitions.

Q17: *What needs to be improved?*

Answer: Mixing students who are genuinely athletic with those who are just 'filling slots' in extracurricular groups creates distraction during focused training sessions. Ideally, serious athletes should be trained separately. Also, budgeting for continuous training — like taking swimming athletes to the pool regularly — should be formally included in the school budget.

Q18: *Will the program continue?*

Answer: Definitely. Sports provides students with self-actualization that academics cannot. In sports, arts, and vocational skills, these students can truly compete. Sports also promotes a healthy lifestyle — a value we as teachers must model for ourselves as well.

TEACHER – LILIANA SARI

Q1: *How long have you been involved in the sports program?*

Answer: My name is Liliana Sari, homeroom teacher for the elementary level (SDLB). I have been in special education since 2010 — 16 years. My first experience was in 2010, accompanying a Down Syndrome student in a 50-meter sprint at the national level in the SOINA Games. That experience deepened my love for children with special needs, especially those with intellectual disabilities and Down Syndrome.

Q2: *What is your main role?*

Answer: During competitions, I served as coach and companion. For SDLB students, sports classes rarely have a dedicated PE teacher, so homeroom teachers handle all subjects including PE, religious education, and sports. When a student shows potential, we are appointed as coach and companion for competitions.

Q3: *How do you assess student involvement in sports activities?*

Answer: Sports is a key developmental activity for children with Down Syndrome. They face challenges in both gross and fine motor skills, and sports — even simple ones done inside the classroom — is one of the most effective tools for their development. Activities like throwing and catching a ball train eye-hand coordination and emotional closeness with the teacher.

Q4: *What factors influence students' willingness to join sports activities?*

Answer: Self-confidence is built from inside the classroom. If we don't build it there, it will be very hard to mobilize them on the field. The most important criterion is: do they understand instructions? Those who understand commands and can be coached are selected first — not based on age or duration of schooling. We also build a partnership with parents to reinforce practice at home.

Q5: *What strategies do you use for all students to be actively involved?*

Answer: For competitions, we select the best candidates. But in the classroom, everyone is trained at their own level. When a child refuses to do something — like throw a bocce ball — we use motivators: 'After you throw the ball, I'll buy you juice, ice cream.' These child-specific approaches are essential because children with special needs require personalized strategies.

Q6: *Are there differences in participation interest between different types of disabilities?*

Answer: Yes, but potential isn't always visible at first. Teachers need to stimulate and discover latent talents. Competition needs also shape which sport a child is trained for. Children whose natural talent aligns with competition requirements are immediately identified; others need more stimulation and trial.

Q7: *How do other students react when they see a peer being active in sports?*

Answer: During Thursday morning exercises, you can clearly see the range: some stand still watching, some move as soon as they hear music, some need teacher prompting. When a child who was static sees a peer moving, curiosity gradually draws them in. A teacher standing alongside and encouraging — 'Come on, try moving your hand like this' — is the bridge.

Q8: *Do you observe physical improvements after sports participation?*

Answer: Even small activities yield big results. For example, asking a child to walk on top of lined-up chairs (20 cm high) to train balance — to others it seems trivial, but to our students it's a significant challenge. After 4–5 sessions, a child who was terrified gradually becomes confident. Repeated practice is the key — no activity for special needs students is without benefit.

Q9: *How do you measure physical improvement?*

Answer: Through personal observation. Since each child has different needs, assessment is individual — either cross-check or descriptive, shared with parents.

Q10: *What forms of adaptation are used?*

Answer: Students who can't do a balance board yet go through simpler steps: walking on lines first, then on tiles, then on the board. For balls: small balls before large ones. Each step is scaffolded based on the child's current ability.

Q11: *Are game rules modified?*

Answer: Yes. In one class there might be students from Grade 2 through Grade 4, with varying cognitive levels. Games are used to teach life skills too — queuing, following rules, teamwork. For example, a simplified basketball game teaches the students how to line up, wait their turn, and move to the back when their turn is over.

Q12: *How effective are adapted tools?*

Answer: Very effective. Varied media keep students engaged. When one activity bores them, switching to another keeps the session going. The diverse Montessori tools in the classroom drawers are introduced at the beginning of the year and used strategically throughout.

Q13: *How does the sports program support students' self-confidence?*

Answer: The school recognizes students who achieve, which motivates their peers. Opportunities are also given not only to winners but rotating based on capacity. This creates a culture where every student has the potential to be recognized.

Q14: *How is social interaction between disabled and non-disabled students?*

Answer: Mild tunagrahita and tunarungu students generally socialize without difficulty when they find compatible peers. Down Syndrome students need more guidance to interact, especially with new people. With support and familiarity, they can connect.

Q15: *What are the main challenges?*

Answer: Finding talent early is the biggest challenge. When older successful students graduate, replacement athletes must be found among younger students whose abilities may not be immediately visible. Identifying which incoming students have potential in sports takes careful observation and creative stimulation.

Q16: *What support do parents and community provide?*

Answer: Multi-stakeholder collaboration is essential: government, school, teachers, and parents must all work together. If parents don't support the activity or can't accompany their child (who may need a companion), the program doesn't run to its full potential. Organizations like SOINA, PEPARDA, and PETAMAS provide the competitive platforms that motivate schools to train students seriously.

Q17: *What is the main strength of the program?*

Answer: Special schools (SLB) focus on student independence — not academics. Sports and arts are the primary channels through which that independence is built. A child who cannot read may be a national-level athlete with rows of trophies at home. Each program complements the others.

Q18: *What needs improvement?*

Answer: First, more deliberate talent identification — not random assignment. Second, teachers as multi-role practitioners must improve their competence in sports they're assigned to coach, even if that means learning from scratch. Building student self-confidence is also critical: many children say 'I can't, I don't want to' even when they clearly have the ability.

Q19: *Will the program continue?*

Answer: Yes, as long as competitive platforms exist. The existence of competitions gives meaning to the training done in school. Without those platforms, students' potential remains hidden.

TEACHER – RINI AGUSTA

Q1: How long have you been involved in the sports program?

Answer: My name is Rini Agusta. I have been teaching here since 1989 — 37 years. I will be retiring in August this year. I have taught students with various disabilities: tunagrahita, Down Syndrome, and teenagers at the SMA level. I also hold additional administrative roles — previously as Vice Principal for Student Affairs, now for Curriculum.

Q2: What is your main role?

Answer: As a homeroom teacher and as Vice Principal for Curriculum, my involvement is in planning and supervising the extracurricular and sports programs. The actual sports instruction is done by the subject PE teacher (currently Bu Dea). I provide oversight and direction. Program planning is done by a team — the PE teacher drafts the program, the team discusses it, and it is then presented to the principal.

Q3: How do you assess students' involvement in sports?

Answer: Every Thursday, students participate in senam (exercise) together — teachers and students. This is part of the sports program. When other classes have PE outside, students from other rooms also want to join — showing genuine enthusiasm for sports. Tunagrahita, tunarungu, and other disability types all mix and play together — in football, badminton, bocce, and long jump.

Q4: What influences students' enthusiasm?

Answer: First, encouragement from teachers and parents. Students need to be continuously motivated with concrete examples: 'Your friend trained hard, won a trophy, and got announced at the flag ceremony. Do you want that too?' Giving students tangible, visible incentives — like seeing their peers rewarded publicly — drives motivation.

Q5: What strategies are used to ensure all students participate?

Answer: We provide concrete, repeated motivational cues. We tell students: 'Those who are diligent and well-behaved get selected; those who are lazy and misbehave don't.' The students may not fully understand abstract reasoning, but they respond to clear cause-and-effect language. Consistent encouragement, gradually internalized, changes their behavior.

Q6: Do you see differences in participation interest across disability types?

Answer: Not really — they are all the same in spirit. They play together regardless of disability type. They observe each other and respond to one another. The only difference they notice is that some friends 'can't speak' (tunarungu), but they don't conceptualize 'disability categories.'

Q7: How do other students respond when a peer wins?

Answer: They express mild jealousy or longing: 'Your friend won yesterday.' This is actually healthy — it shows they have desire and awareness. Teachers channel that feeling into constructive motivation for future events.

Q8: Do you observe physical improvements?

Answer: Yes. We can see clear physical differences between students who regularly exercise and those who don't — in their physique, agility, and coordination. For bocce players, the improvement is visible in their focus and precision of rolling the ball.

Q9: *What adaptations are provided?*

Answer: Training is adapted to each student's ability level. Equipment and tasks are also adjusted accordingly. Everything — from tools to training intensity — is tailored to the student's physical and cognitive capacity.

Q10: *How does sports help self-confidence?*

Answer: Students gain confidence by meeting peers from other schools at events. They socialize, interact, and even make new friends. Interestingly, the students themselves are often calm and relaxed at competitions — it's the accompanying teacher who is most stressed! Students with Down Syndrome especially seem unbothered by competitive pressure.

Q11: *How is social interaction with non-disabled peers at events?*

Answer: Our competitions are typically within the disability community — we don't yet integrate with regular schools at events. Within the school itself, all disability types mix freely. Students with physical disabilities (tunadaksa) in wheelchairs are even assisted by their peers without being asked.

Q12: *What are the main challenges?*

Answer: The main challenge is parental collaboration. Sometimes parents leave everything to the school. Without joint effort between school and family, the student's development is limited. We still work to bridge that gap through ongoing communication and encouragement.

Q13: *Are facilities adequate?*

Answer: Alhamdulillah — the school is quite well-equipped. All necessary equipment is available.

Q14: *What is the main strength?*

Answer: Teamwork within the school — between the sports team, curriculum team, and school leadership. Combined with budget support and regular program evaluation, the program is sustainable and effective.

Q15: *Will the program continue?*

Answer: Yes. The sports extracurricular program is planned annually and evaluated regularly. It is not a one-time initiative — it's built into the school calendar and continuously reviewed for improvement.

TEACHER – ROSMADAWATI

Q1: *How long have you been involved in the sports program?*

Answer: At this school, approximately 2 years — I transferred here in 2023. But I have worked with students with disabilities at other schools before.

Q2: *What is your main role?*

Answer: For students preparing for competition, my role is to train them in the specific event they'll compete in — teaching the techniques, explaining the competition rules, and clarifying what is evaluated.

Q3: *How do you assess students' involvement in sports?*

Answer: Tunagrahita students understand the concept of competition, unlike students with other disabilities who may not. Some students say 'I can't do it, Bu' — and it's our job as teachers to instill belief: 'You can, let's practice first.' If left to themselves, they won't volunteer. Our encouragement is essential.

Q4: *What factors influence students' enthusiasm?*

Answer: Teacher motivation is the primary driver — we build their self-belief so they feel capable. Once that inner confidence is established, they are brave enough to join competitions.

Q5: *Do you see differences in participation interest across disabilities?*

Answer: It varies by individual, not by disability type. Some tunagrahita students have high self-confidence and are eager to compete; others are reserved. Compared to students with other types of disability, tunagrahita students understand the concept of winning and losing, while others may not — they just run because everyone runs, without understanding the competitive context.

Q6: *How do other students respond when a peer is active in sports?*

Answer: They become more enthusiastic too — seeing an active peer motivates others to join.

Q7: *Do you observe physical improvements?*

Answer: Yes — students who regularly engage in sports appear more physically fit. Runners, for example, show improved physical condition compared to before training.

Q8: *How do you measure physical improvement?*

Answer: By observing strength, posture, and resilience — students appear more upright, stronger, and more capable over time.

Q9: *What adaptations are used in training?*

Answer: Training is tailored to each student's capacity. For example, if a student cannot run 200 meters, we start with 100 meters and build from there.

Q10: *Are game rules modified?*

Answer: Yes — both in games and classroom activities. Modifications are made according to the student's needs. For example, students who need to develop fine motor skills are given textured balls (spiky balls) to hold and squeeze.

Q11: *How effective are the adaptations?*

Answer: Very beneficial. When training and tools are matched to a student's needs, the impact is clear and meaningful.

Q12: *How does sports affect self-confidence?*

Answer: Before competing, students are usually not confident. But once on the field — when they see some competitors who are less skilled than them — their confidence grows. After winning, their enthusiasm doubles.

Q13: *How is social interaction with non-disabled peers?*

Answer: For tunagrahita students, communication and socialization are generally not a problem. They can interact with non-disabled children outside school. After winning a competition, they are often praised by neighborhood friends, which makes them proud.

Q14: *What are the main challenges?*

Answer: Convincing students to participate is the hardest part. Some refuse at first, and teachers sometimes have to visit their homes just to persuade them to attend the competition.

Q15: *Are facilities adequate?*

Answer: Some are, some aren't. For example, the javelin throw field is too narrow. We make use of whatever space is available.

Q16: *What support does the school, parents, and community provide?*

Answer: Support is provided, though limited. When a proper field is unavailable, we use available space creatively.

Q17: *What is the main strength?*

Answer: Sports increases students' enthusiasm, improves physical fitness, and provides an outlet for their talents. For tunagrahita students whose IQ is lower, their potential in sports can be fully realized and give them a sense of achievement.

Q18: *What needs improvement?*

Answer: We need more specialized PE teachers or external coaches with genuine expertise in the sports we teach — especially for competitive events like badminton. Homeroom teachers like us have general knowledge but may not have deep expertise in specific sports techniques.

Q19: *Will the program continue?*

Answer: Yes — now that we have a dedicated PE teacher, the program is better positioned. Sports not only supports performance but fundamentally serves the students' health and well-being.

SECTION B: PARENT INTERVIEWS

PARENT – GUSLINA

Q1: *Can you introduce yourself and tell us about your child?*

Answer: My name is Lina. I am the parent and guardian of my twins Zikra and Zikri. After assessment, they were diagnosed with tunagrahita, speech delay, and short attention span. Now they are 16 years old. When they were 7, they couldn't speak. We took them to Padang for therapy at Semen Padang Hospital — physically they were normal, but they were referred here for both schooling and therapy. After 7 years, they can now speak (with some speech imperfections), read, count, and manage basic self-care independently.

Q2: *How long have your children been in the sports program?*

Answer: They have been at this school for 7 years. They've been seriously engaged in football for about a year. In general PE, they participate every week on the scheduled sports day.

Q3: *Do you observe their interest in sports?*

Answer: Yes — they are enthusiastic. They often wear their football jersey to school on sports days. At home, they enjoy watching football matches on TV.

Q4: *Are they consistent in attending training?*

Answer: Yes — every week they follow the scheduled sports session without being reminded.

Q5: *Do they need motivation from you to attend?*

Answer: No — they know their sports schedule and look forward to it. They remind each other: 'Tomorrow is sports day, we play football.'

Q6: *Do you see physical changes after joining sports activities?*

Answer: Yes — visible physical development and improved strength. They are hardy — indifferent to rain or sun. They are also rarely sick now.

Q7: *Do they appear more independent after joining sports?*

Answer: Yes — after sports days, they wash their own sports clothes without being told.

Q8: *Has their self-confidence increased?*

Answer: Yes — their self-confidence has improved.

Q9: *How is their social interaction with friends?*

Answer: They are selective with friends — they know which friends treat them well and which don't. They distance themselves from those who mock or trick them.

Q10: *Do they seem happier and more enthusiastic?*

Answer: Yes — they're always excited about the next activity. They sleep soundly after school — by 8 PM, and wake up refreshed in the morning.

Q11: *Are they becoming more confident speaking in public?*

Answer: Not yet for public speaking — they still tend to be shy in crowds. That still needs improvement.

Q12: *Do they talk about making new friends at sports?*

Answer: Yes — they sometimes mention new friends by name when they come home.

Q13: *How do you view the school's support?*

Answer: The support is more than sufficient. Alhamdulillah.

Q14: *What is the role of teachers and coaches?*

Answer: The teachers are focused and dedicated to teaching the children.

Q15: *Have you encountered any obstacles?*

Answer: None — everything has been smooth and enjoyable for the children.

Q16: *What is the greatest benefit of the sports program?*

Answer: After school and sports, they sleep well and wake up energized. The activity gives structure and energy management to their day.

Q17: *What needs to be improved?*

Answer: Nothing major — they enjoy football and the current activities seem adequate. Perhaps more variety like basketball when they're ready.

PARENT – HERLINA DEWIFERI

Q1: *Can you introduce your child?*

Answer: My child is Pajri (Fajri), born in 2010 — now 16 years old. Even before going to school, he was naturally active — going off on his own, walking to the river to collect stones, active all day. He usually doesn't come home until Maghrib (evening prayer time).

Q2: *How long has he been in the sports program?*

Answer: Fajri transferred from SD 01 to this school around Grade 4 to 5 of elementary school. He is now in SMA Grade 1 here.

Q3: *What is his main interest in sports?*

Answer: His hobby is badminton (bulu tangkis). He frequently joins competitions and often wins. There are already many trophies at home.

Q4: *Is he consistent in training?*

Answer: Very much so — when there's an upcoming competition, he trains enthusiastically with other teachers. Even when there's no competition, he stays motivated because teachers remind him, 'Fajri, we'll have a chance soon — keep training, you'll be selected.'

Q5: *Has his interest in sports changed since joining the school?*

Answer: It remains focused on badminton, though he also participates in other available sports. His competitive drive is strong — he participates in various competitions.

Q6: *Is he enthusiastic about competitions and training?*

Answer: Yes — very enthusiastic. His enthusiasm grows with every competition he joins.

Q7: *Does he need encouragement from you?*

Answer: He needs both his own drive and encouragement from teachers — both play a role.

Q8: *Is he more active at home after sports activities?*

Answer: He remains active both in and out of school.

Q9: *Has his health improved?*

Answer: Yes — he's rarely sick, even though he's often out in the sun or rain, or down at the river. His physical endurance is notably strong.

Q10: *Has sport made him more independent?*

Answer: Yes. When there's no food at home, he cooks his own noodles. He is self-sufficient in daily tasks.

Q11: *Has his self-confidence increased?*

Answer: Very much — he's not shy around anyone. He is confident in performing and presenting himself.

Q12: *How is his social life with peers?*

Answer: He gets along well with everyone — no issues at school or in the neighborhood. Friends come to the house to pick him up.

Q13: *Does he seem happier and more enthusiastic after sports?*

Answer: Yes — he is energized and happy. The prizes and trophies he wins also bring him a sense of pride and material satisfaction.

Q14: *Does he talk about new friends he meets at competitions?*

Answer: Yes — he talks about meeting competitors from other schools. He mentions that sometimes the opponents are much bigger than him, which he finds amusing.

Q15: *What do you think about the school's support?*

Answer: The school support is good. He's been able to participate in many different types of competitions thanks to school facilitation.

Q16: *How do you view the teachers and coaches?*

Answer: They are good — understanding and engaged. They train the students with dedication.

Q17: *What obstacles have you encountered?*

Answer: The biggest challenge at home is study time. His mother is not literate, so academic support at home is limited. His older brother sometimes helps, but it's inconsistent.

Q18: *What is the greatest benefit of the program?*

Answer: Sports helps him meet friends from other schools and broadens his social network beyond his immediate community.

Q19: *What needs to be improved?*

Answer: Fajri can be slow in some things, but other teachers understand his pace and work with him accordingly.

PARENT – IKHSAN ENDRIZUL

Q1: *Can you tell us about your child?*

Answer: My child is 17 years old. At home, he's relaxed and mainly plays on his phone.

Q2: *How did your child become interested in sports?*

Answer: Our house is close to a river, so from a young age he swam there naturally. That early exposure led to interest in competitive swimming.

Q3: *Has he been consistent in training?*

Answer: He's been in the river regularly since childhood — it's a natural habit more than structured practice.

Q4: *Have you observed changes in his motivation for sports?*

Answer: He has remained focused on swimming and running — his interest hasn't shifted to other sports.

Q5: *Does he anticipate training schedules eagerly?*

Answer: He's fairly relaxed about it — not overly excited, but willing.

Q6: *Does he need parental encouragement to train?*

Answer: No — he joins on his own initiative.

Q7: *Has his physical condition improved?*

Answer: Yes — moderately improved.

Q8: *Is he often sick?*

Answer: No — he rarely gets sick.

Q9: *Is he more active at home?*

Answer: His activity level at home remains about the same.

Q10: *Has he become more independent?*

Answer: Yes — there is some improvement in his independence.

Q11: *Has his self-confidence increased?*

Answer: Yes — he's increasingly confident in performing and presenting himself.

Q12: *How is his social interaction with peers?*

Answer: He tends to stay home and communicate less with peers outside — but some interaction does exist.

Q13: *Is he happier and more enthusiastic overall?*

Answer: Yes — he is more energized, especially after winning.

Q14: *Is he more confident speaking up?*

Answer: In crowds, he tends to be quiet. He expresses emotion privately — happy or angry depending on whether he's been bothered.

Q15: *Does he talk about new friends from events?*

Answer: Yes — he mentions meeting children from other schools at competitions.

Q16: *How many times has he won?*

Answer: Approximately 3–4 times.

PARENT – JUSNIWATI

Q1: *Can you introduce yourself and your child?*

Answer: My child is 15–16 years old with tunagrahita disability. Communication is somewhat slow — she understands things but processes them more gradually.

Q2: *How long has your child been in the sports program?*

Answer: She participates in sports at school — the program is based there.

Q3: *Do you observe her interest in sports?*

Answer: Not particularly at home — she tends to stay indoors. She does occasionally jog in the neighborhood with friends.

Q4: *Does she enjoy school sports activities?*

Answer: She participates in school PE, and occasionally jogs in the village.

Q5: *What motivates her interest in sports?*

Answer: It's difficult to pinpoint — it seems more situational, driven by school context.

Q6: *Does she talk about school or sports at home?*

Answer: Not really — she doesn't often share details about her day.

Q7: *Has she become physically stronger after sports?*

Answer: Yes — physically she seems stronger.

Q8: *Is she often sick?*

Answer: She does get sick occasionally, but it's not severe — no fever, usually just minor discomfort.

Q9: *Has she become more independent?*

Answer: I believe she has some independence, though I'm not always home to observe.

Q10: *Has her self-confidence increased?*

Answer: Not much change is visible at home — she receives praise and encouragement at school, but this doesn't seem to carry over significantly to home behavior.

Q11: *How are her social relationships at home?*

Answer: She plays with neighborhood children — both boys and girls in the area, including friends from SMA.

Q12: *Does she talk about new friends from sports?*

Answer: No — she doesn't often share details like that.

Q13: *What do you think about the school's support?*

Answer: I'm not certain of the full scope — I'm often at work when she's home. I don't know all the details of the school's activities.

Q14: *Have you accompanied her to competitions?*

Answer: No — I entrust her to the teachers and coaches.

Q15: *What obstacles are there in sports activities?*

Answer: At home there is no sports infrastructure — sports only happen at school.

Q16: *What is the greatest benefit?*

Answer: She is more active through the school setting — the structured program keeps her engaged.

PARENT – ELI YARNI

Q1: *Can you introduce your child?*

Answer: My son Rio is 15 years old with tunagrahita disability. At home he mostly plays inside since the neighborhood children are typically developing, and he has been bullied before — so he rarely goes outside except for prayers at the mosque.

Q2: *How long has Rio been in the sports program?*

Answer: He has been at this school for 7 years, with sports every Thursday.

Q3: *Do you see his interest in sports?*

Answer: Yes — he seems to enjoy playing football, but at the elementary level (SD), sports at school are still very general and not yet specialized.

Q4: *Is Rio enthusiastic about sports?*

Answer: When he gets tired, he becomes less enthusiastic. But generally, when with friends, he is happy and active.

Q5: *Does he need encouragement to join?*

Answer: Yes — some encouragement is needed, especially when he's tired.

Q6: *Has his physical condition improved after sports?*

Answer: Yes — you can see that he has more energy. He's also healthier — rarely sick since doing regular sports.

Q7: *Has sports made him more independent?*

Answer: He talks more — sharing what he learns at school with his father at home.

Q8: *Has his self-confidence increased?*

Answer: Yes — somewhat, though it still needs continued development. At the SD level, sports are not yet specialized, so focused confidence-building through sports will likely come at the SMP stage.

Q9: *How are his social relationships?*

Answer: At school he has friends; at home he has fewer due to the bullying history.

Q10: *Does he seem happier overall?*

Answer: Yes — he's happy doing physical activities. He seems joyful when running around.

Q11: *What is the school's support like?*

Answer: He needs a parent or familiar figure to be present — when I was late arriving for one sports event, he refused to enter. He needs security and presence.

Q12: *What are the main challenges?*

Answer: He lacks focus without a companion. He needs a dedicated coach or teacher who is consistently present and focused on him.

Q13: *What is the greatest benefit of the sports program?*

Answer: Going to school gives him motivation — he's energized when there are activities. When his previous teacher was absent for a while and came back, he immediately showed excitement.

Q14: *What needs to be improved?*

Answer: His ability to focus independently. He needs a consistent, dedicated companion to help build his independence and concentration in sports.

PARENT – MUNIARTI

Q1: *Can you introduce your child?*

Answer: My son's name is Khalid (Kholit). He is 18 years old. His school attendance is irregular — sometimes he goes, sometimes he doesn't.

Q2: *How long has he been in the sports program?*

Answer: From Grade 2 of SMP until now in SMA Grade 1.

Q3: *What are his sports achievements?*

Answer: He tried swimming when he was in SMP — and suddenly came in second place. His teachers told me he has real talent in swimming.

Q4: *Is he consistent in training?*

Answer: Training at the school pool level is available, but consistent pool access is limited.

Q5: *Has his motivation changed since joining sports?*

Answer: Yes — he is more motivated to come to school when there are sports activities.

Q6: *Does he wait eagerly for training schedules?*

Answer: He is enthusiastic on the day of sports (Fridays).

Q7: *Does he need encouragement to participate?*

Answer: Yes — some encouragement from me is needed.

Q8: *Has his physical condition improved?*

Answer: His physical endurance has improved — he is more resilient.

Q9: *Is he more active at home?*

Answer: Yes — he is somewhat more active.

Q10: *Has he become more independent?*

Answer: Yes — he shows greater independence in daily tasks.

Q11: *Has his self-confidence increased?*

Answer: Yes — his self-confidence has grown through sports participation.

Q12: *How are his social relationships at home?*

Answer: He plays with neighborhood children, including traditional games. He is active socially around the house.

Q13: *Does he talk about school activities at home?*

Answer: Yes — he tells me about planting vegetables and other school activities (oledon/gardening).

Q14: *Does he talk about new friends from competitions?*

Answer: He is excited about upcoming events — particularly swimming. He's second in running but more enthusiastic about swimming.

Q15: *Do you accompany him to competitions?*

Answer: No — I leave him with his teachers and coaches. Training is done entirely at school.

Q16: *What is the benefit of the sports program?*

Answer: It gives him motivation and structure. He looks forward to activities and his overall mood and engagement improve on sports days.

PARENT – RENI SURYANI

Q1: *Can you introduce your child Imam?*

Answer: Imam is a teenager with tunagrahita disability. His daily life is normal — he is active and participates in community activities like Posyandu Remaja (youth health program).

Q2: *How long has he been doing sports?*

Answer: Since elementary school.

Q3: *Does he often join competitions?*

Answer: Yes — he has joined many competitions and has won.

Q4: *Why is Imam interested in sports rather than academics?*

Answer: He naturally tends toward physical activity more than theoretical study. His IQ is below average for academic subjects, but in sports he thrives.

Q5: *Does he need encouragement to join sports?*

Answer: No — it's his own desire. I just follow his lead and support him.

Q6: *Has his physical condition improved?*

Answer: Yes — his physical endurance has improved since being active in sports.

Q7: *Does he help at home?*

Answer: Not much in terms of household tasks.

Q8: *How many times has he won competitions?*

Answer: Many times across different sports — including high jump. He participates in multiple events.

Q9: *Is he happier after participating in sports?*

Answer: He's always happy — sports keeps his spirits up. He also participates in traditional arts (randai), which contributes to his expressiveness.

Q10: *Does he feel more confident expressing himself?*

Answer: Yes — participating in randai (traditional performance art) has made him more comfortable expressing himself in front of others.

Q11: *What do you think about the school's support?*

Answer: The school's support is good.

Q12: *Do you accompany him to competitions?*

Answer: Yes — I go to watch him compete.

Q13: *Do other parents show appreciation for his achievements?*

Answer: Other parents at the school notice and appreciate his achievements.

Q14: *Would you recommend this school to others with children with special needs?*

Answer: Yes — I know others who were initially hesitant about SLB, but after seeing the environment and results, they came to appreciate it.

Q15: *Is there bullying at school or at home?*

Answer: No bullying — not at school, and not in the neighborhood either.

LAMPIRAN

DATA HASIL WAWANCARA

Partisipasi Olahraga, Kebugaran Fisik, Kesejahteraan Psikososial,
dan Tantangan Program Olahraga bagi Siswa Tunagrahita

BAGIAN A: WAWANCARA GURU

GURU – DHEA PUTRI DEFIYANTI

P1: *Sudah berapa lama Ibu terlibat dalam pengelolaan atau pengajaran program olahraga di sekolah ini?*

Jawaban: Saya mulai bekerja di SLB dari tahun 2014. Sebelumnya di SLB 2 Lubuk Buaya, sekarang di SLB 1 Negeri Padang. Kurang lebih sudah 10 tahun, di dua sekolah tersebut.

P2: *Apa peran utama Ibu dalam menjalankan program olahraga tersebut?*

Jawaban: Peran saya di sini sebagai guru olahraga, pendamping, dan pelatih. Di SLB, anak-anak dikelompokkan dan setiap tahun ada perlombaan yang diikuti. Saya bersama rekan guru lainnya menyeleksi anak-anak yang dinilai mampu mengikuti lomba, mirip seperti seleksi di sekolah reguler. Pertama dilihat kondisi fisik dan kesehatannya, kemudian bagaimana ia merespons perintah, karena rata-rata anak tunagrahita memiliki IQ di bawah 90.

P3: *Bagaimana tingkat keterlibatan siswa dengan disabilitas dalam kegiatan olahraga?*

Jawaban: Saya mengajar penjaskes 2 jam untuk kelas SMP dan SMA yang digabung, tidak dipisahkan berdasarkan jenis ketunaan karena keterbatasan jam. Untuk anak tunagrahita yang digabung dengan tunarungu masih bisa berjalan baik, tetapi jika ada anak autis dengan tingkat tantrum tinggi, pengelolaan menjadi lebih sulit karena autis dan tunagrahita cenderung berlawanan pendekatannya.

P4: *Hal-hal apa yang mempengaruhi semangat dan keputusan siswa untuk berpartisipasi?*

Jawaban: Anak-anak tunagrahita membutuhkan motivasi. Saya memberi mereka janji dan harapan: 'Kalau kamu semangat dan menang, kamu mau apa? Nanti Ibu ajak ke sini.' Beberapa siswa laki-laki dengan campuran tunalaras perlu pendekatan yang lebih tegas namun konstruktif, seperti sikap yang tegas demi kemajuan mereka.

P5: *Strategi apa yang Ibu gunakan agar semua siswa terlibat aktif?*

Jawaban: Berbeda dengan guru di sekolah reguler, kami tidak bisa sekadar memberi perintah. Kami harus turun langsung. Jika siswa tunagrahita berat (C1) berlari zigzag, saya ikut berlari mendampingi satu per satu. Jika saya hanya mencontohkan dari jauh, mereka hanya diam. Ketika guru memegang tangan atau berlari bersama mereka, mereka menjadi bahagia dan semangat.

P6: *Apakah ada perbedaan minat partisipasi berdasarkan jenis disabilitas?*

Jawaban: Perbedaannya lebih kepada mood masing-masing anak, bukan jenis ketunaan. Ada tunagrahita yang tidak mood, ada juga tunarungu yang demikian. Di SLB, saya belajar bahwa kita harus menyesuaikan dengan keinginan anak, bukan keinginan kita.

P7: *Bagaimana tanggapan siswa disabilitas lainnya melihat teman mereka aktif berolahraga?*

Jawaban: Jiwa sosial dan tolong-menolong di sini luar biasa. Misalnya, ketika saya membawa rombongan jalan jauh dan ada siswa tunadaksa yang kesulitan berjalan, teman-temannya yang tunagrahita bergantian memegangnya, menyemangatinya, bahkan menyanyikan lagu untuknya. Ketika air liurnya keluar pun, mereka yang mengelapkan. Setia kawan mereka sungguh luar biasa.

P8: Apakah ada peningkatan kemampuan fisik siswa setelah mengikuti program olahraga?

Jawaban: Ada. Contohnya Fajri – awalnya dia malas. Dengan program latihan dan motivasi yang intens, akhirnya ia juara satu lompat jauh di WNP. Ada perubahan nyata, terutama jika semangat ditanamkan dengan kuat. Fisik Fajri seperti orang normal, hanya komunikasinya yang setara anak SD meski sudah SMA.

P9: Bentuk penyesuaian apa yang Ibu berikan kepada siswa?

Jawaban: Pengelompokan sangat penting. Saya tidak mencampur siswa tunagrahita C biasa dengan C1 karena kemampuannya sangat berbeda. Siswa C1 hanya bisa mengikuti olahraga tertentu seperti bocce, yang hanya membutuhkan koordinasi tangan ringan tanpa tenaga ekstra. C dan tunarungu bisa digabung, tetapi C1 dan autis harus dipisah.

P10: Apakah ada aturan permainan yang dimodifikasi?

Jawaban: Bocce, misalnya, memang sudah dirancang khusus untuk anak Down Syndrome, sudah ada di Paralimpik dan telah dimodifikasi oleh SOINA (Special Olympics Indonesia). Ini adalah permainan bola kecil yang menyerupai bowling yang dimodifikasi.

P11: Bagaimana efektivitas alat bantu olahraga yang disesuaikan?

Jawaban: Di sini kami menggunakan peralatan standar, bola-bola biasa seperti basket, voli, dan bola kaki. Karena tidak ada siswa tunanetra, kami tidak memerlukan bola khusus berbunyi. Sekolah menyediakan anggaran olahraga setiap semester untuk kelengkapan peralatan standar.

P12: Sejauh mana program olahraga membantu meningkatkan rasa percaya diri siswa?

Jawaban: Sangat jauh dampaknya. Contoh nyata adalah Fajri. Sebelum saya datang, belum ada guru olahraga selama dua tahun. Fajri dikenal sulit ditangani. Guru-guru senior yang sudah mendekati pensiun kehabisan energi menghadapinya. Saya coba pendekatan tegas setelah berkonsultasi dengan rekan. Setelah ia menang lomba dan dipanggil di upacara sekolah, kepercayaan dirinya melonjak drastis. Ia mulai berani tampil di upacara, sesuatu yang tidak pernah dilakukannya sebelumnya. Kini ia selalu bertanya, 'Bu, kapan tanding lagi?'

P13: Bagaimana interaksi sosial siswa disabilitas dengan teman non-disabilitas?

Jawaban: Dari pengamatan di media sosial, siswa tunagrahita ringan (C biasa) masih bisa berteman dan aktif di media sosial dengan teman luar sekolah. Untuk C1 mungkin lebih terbatas. Fajri suka berimajinasi, sering bercerita hal-hal di luar nalar saat istirahat, dan saya menanggapinya seperti teman agar ia merasa nyaman.

P14: Apakah program olahraga sudah menciptakan lingkungan yang inklusif?

Jawaban: Sudah, sangat baik. Sosialisasi antar siswa di sini, baik tunagrahita, tunarungu, maupun tunadaksa, sangat bagus. Rasa kesetiakawanan mereka jauh melebihi yang ada di sekolah reguler. Di kantin pun, siswa yang tidak ada pendamping orang tua selalu dibantu oleh temannya yang lebih mampu. Itulah alasan saya bertahan di SLB ini.

P15: Apa kendala utama dalam menjalankan program olahraga inklusif?

Jawaban: Kendala terbesar saya secara pribadi adalah menghadapi siswa autis. Saya tidak memiliki latar belakang pendidikan luar biasa (PLB), sehingga ketika mereka tantrum – memukul, melempar – saya belum tahu cara yang tepat untuk menanganinya.

P16: *Apakah sumber daya dan fasilitas sekolah mencukupi?*

Jawaban: Sangat mencukupi. Kami memiliki anggaran setiap semester, tidak hanya untuk olahraga tetapi untuk semua program. Fasilitas sekolah sangat lengkap: tata busana, tata boga, tata kecantikan, musik dengan band lengkap. Dibandingkan SMK, fasilitas SLB Negeri ini sering lebih lengkap.

P17: *Bagaimana dukungan dari sekolah, orang tua, dan komunitas?*

Jawaban: Sekolah sangat mendukung. Setiap ada perlombaan, saya langsung dipanggil untuk koordinasi dan seleksi siswa, dan sekolah memfasilitasi transportasi dan konsumsi. Orang tua juga sangat antusias; beberapa bahkan meminta agar anaknya diikutsertakan. Kami berusaha adil dan realistis soal kesiapan anak. Orang tua di sini luar biasa – mereka menunggu dari pagi hingga sore setiap hari.

P18: *Apa keunggulan utama dari program olahraga ini?*

Jawaban: Pertama, fasilitas. Dibandingkan SLB swasta, sebagai SLB Negeri kami mendapat dukungan penuh dari pemerintah. Tersedia semua peralatan, bahkan ada asrama. Guru tidak perlu pusing mencari tempat atau memodifikasi alat. Kelengkapan fasilitas adalah pendukung terbesar.

P19: *Bagian mana dari program yang masih perlu dikembangkan?*

Jawaban: Saya berharap identifikasi bakat bisa dilakukan lebih dini, idealnya sejak tingkat SD. Saat ini seleksi baru dilakukan dari SMP yang sudah tanggung dari segi usia untuk pertandingan olahraga yang memiliki kategori umur. Jika bisa dimulai dari SD, hasilnya akan jauh lebih optimal.

P20: *Apakah Ibu yakin program ini akan terus berlanjut?*

Jawaban: Sangat yakin. Dengan adanya organisasi seperti PERNAS, SOINA, dan Special Olympics, anak-anak berprestasi akan terus maju. Ada 3 perlombaan per tahun di berbagai tingkat, mulai dari Kota Padang, Provinsi, hingga nasional, termasuk SOINA, ODSN, dan seleksi Paralimpik. Sekolah memfasilitasi semua kebutuhan: transportasi, konsumsi, dan logistik.

GURU – FITRIANI

P1: *Sudah berapa lama Ibu terlibat dalam program olahraga di sekolah ini?*

Jawaban: Di SLB, pembelajaran olahraga dengan guru penjaskes khusus hanya ada di tingkat SMP dan SMA. Di tingkat SD, wali kelas bertanggung jawab penuh atas semua mata pelajaran termasuk olahraga. Saya sudah mengajar sejak tahun 2000, hampir 26 tahun.

P2: *Apa peran utama Ibu dalam program olahraga?*

Jawaban: Peran utama saya adalah sebagai pembimbing, pendamping, dan pelatih. Siswa tunagrahita tidak bisa diunggulkan di bidang akademik, sehingga kita fokus bagaimana mereka bisa berprestasi melalui jalur non-akademik. Olahraga adalah salah satu saluran yang paling efektif bagi mereka.

P3: *Bagaimana tingkat keterlibatan siswa dalam kegiatan olahraga?*

Jawaban: Siswa tunagrahita umumnya antusias dan berbakat di bidang olahraga. Ketika ditantang dengan perlombaan, mereka menjadi sangat serius dalam berlatih. Orang tua pun mendukung penuh – mereka siap standby mengantar dan menemani anak ke tempat pertandingan.

P4: *Apa yang mempengaruhi semangat dan keputusan siswa untuk berpartisipasi?*

Jawaban: Tiga faktor utama: (1) kemampuan siswa sendiri di bidang olahraga, (2) dukungan orang tua, dan (3) cara pembimbingan yang dilakukan oleh pelatih. Ketersediaan sarana-prasarana seperti raket dan bola untuk latihan juga berperan.

P5: *Strategi apa yang digunakan agar semua siswa terlibat aktif?*

Jawaban: Kita harus jeli melihat kondisi emosional anak. Jangan sampai mereka merasa tidak diperhatikan. Tidak bisa dipaksakan jika tidak mood. Inklusi berarti merangkul apa yang dibutuhkan anak, bukan memaksakan apa yang kita inginkan sebagai guru.

P6: *Apakah ada perbedaan minat berdasarkan jenis disabilitas?*

Jawaban: Lebih bergantung pada kepribadian dan kemampuan individual daripada jenis ketunaan. Di antara siswa tunagrahita ada yang mampu didik (masih bisa akademik) dan mampu latih (lebih cocok latihan vokasional). Keduanya bisa berprestasi di olahraga tergantung potensi masing-masing.

P7: *Bagaimana reaksi siswa lain ketika teman mereka aktif berolahraga?*

Jawaban: Mereka sangat mendukung. Ketika ada siswa yang memenangkan perlombaan, namanya diumumkan pada upacara hari Senin dan penghargaan diserahkan di depan seluruh siswa. Ini memotivasi yang lain untuk juga ingin dipilih dan diakui.

P8: *Apakah ada peningkatan kemampuan fisik setelah mengikuti program?*

Jawaban: Ya. Siswa yang aktif mengikuti senam pagi hari Kamis menunjukkan peningkatan kebugaran yang signifikan dibandingkan yang hanya hadir seadanya. Aktivitas fisik rutin membangun stamina dan kekuatan mereka.

P9: *Adaptasi apa yang diberikan dalam latihan fisik?*

Jawaban: Di sekolah kami, peralatan yang digunakan masih standar. Modifikasi lebih banyak diterapkan untuk siswa tunarungu, misalnya bola ping-pong dengan bunyi. Untuk siswa tunagrahita, modifikasi alat khusus biasanya tidak diperlukan.

P10: *Bagaimana dampak olahraga terhadap kepercayaan diri dan kesejahteraan psikososial siswa?*

Jawaban: Dampaknya sangat jelas. Ada satu siswa tunarungu yang sebelumnya menolak bersosialisasi dan berteman. Setelah memenangkan perlombaan, ia perlahan membuka diri, mulai berteman, dan menjadi lebih termotivasi dalam berbagai aspek kehidupan.

P11: *Bagaimana interaksi sosial antara siswa disabilitas dan non-disabilitas?*

Jawaban: Melalui kegiatan olahraga bersama di lapangan, interaksi sosial terjadi secara alami. Siswa dari berbagai sekolah dan latar belakang bertemu dan membentuk ikatan. Yang awalnya asing perlahan menjadi akrab, bahkan membentuk kelompok pertemanan.

P12: *Apa tantangan utama dalam pelaksanaan program olahraga inklusif?*

Jawaban: Tantangan utama adalah kesenjangan pengetahuan teknis. Sebagai guru dengan latar belakang pendidikan umum, bukan pelatihan olahraga khusus, kami perlu terus belajar teknik yang benar untuk setiap cabang olahraga. Kami khawatir mengajarkan teknik yang kurang tepat kepada siswa.

P13: *Apakah fasilitas dan sumber daya sekolah sudah memadai?*

Jawaban: Masih perlu peningkatan. Setelah renovasi terakhir, peralatan di aula banyak yang rusak atau hilang dan belum sepenuhnya diganti. Lapangan bocce di belakang sudah permanen, tetapi fasilitas lain masih perlu ditingkatkan.

P14: *Apa kekuatan utama dari program olahraga ini?*

Jawaban: Kekuatan terpenting adalah semangat dan dedikasi guru. Jika guru termotivasi, mereka bisa memotivasi siswa. Kami juga perlu terus meningkatkan pengetahuan guru tentang olahraga khusus untuk anak berkebutuhan khusus.

P15: *Apa yang perlu dikembangkan atau diperbaiki?*

Jawaban: Dua hal utama: (1) meningkatkan kompetensi guru melalui pelatihan dan sosialisasi olahraga adaptif, dan (2) meningkatkan fasilitas dan peralatan olahraga dari pihak sekolah.

P16: *Apakah program olahraga akan terus berlanjut?*

Jawaban: Pasti, karena sudah menjadi bagian dari kurikulum resmi (mata pelajaran olahraga). Ada juga kegiatan olahraga terstruktur setiap hari Kamis, di mana siswa ditugaskan ke cabang olahraga masing-masing. Program ini sudah terencana secara sistematis dan dievaluasi secara berkala.

GURU – GEMI SAPUTRI

P1: Sudah berapa lama Ibu terlibat dalam program olahraga di sekolah ini?

Jawaban: Nama saya Gemi Saputri, wali kelas 8 SMPLB Tunagrahita. Saya sudah mengajar 17 tahun. SK PNS saya terbit 2,5 tahun lalu di SLB Negeri ini. Sebelumnya di swasta, saya merangkap sebagai guru olahraga sekaligus wali kelas. Di SLB Negeri, sudah ada guru olahraga khusus yaitu Bu Dea, dan wali kelas berkolaborasi dengannya dalam pembelajaran olahraga.

P2: Apakah Ibu pernah melatih dan mendampingi siswa ke perlombaan?

Jawaban: Pernah, sampai ke tingkat kejuaraan.

P3: Bagaimana tingkat keterlibatan siswa dalam kegiatan olahraga?

Jawaban: Anak-anak dengan disabilitas cenderung lebih suka bergerak daripada duduk belajar. Mereka benar-benar menyukai olahraga. Kalau satu hari saja tidak ada olahraga, mereka sudah ribut. Guru olahraganya pun pandai menghadapi anak-anak sehingga mereka aktif dan bersemangat.

P4: Apa yang mempengaruhi kemauan siswa untuk berpartisipasi?

Jawaban: Pertama, minat anak itu sendiri. Kedua, dorongan dari guru, baik wali kelas maupun guru olahraga, yang menciptakan daya tarik agar siswa termotivasi dan percaya diri untuk ikut lomba.

P5: Strategi apa yang digunakan agar semua siswa aktif berpartisipasi?

Jawaban: Pertama, kita amati olahraga apa yang diminati setiap anak. Tidak semua anak bisa semua olahraga – tergantung minat dan bakat masing-masing. Anak mungkin berminat tapi tidak berbakat, atau berbakat tapi minatnya di tempat lain. Keduanya harus sejalan, dan kita arahkan dengan bijak.

P6: Apakah ada perbedaan minat antara jenis disabilitas yang berbeda?

Jawaban: Perlombaan olahraga di SLB disesuaikan dengan jenis ketunaan. Untuk hambatan intelektual ditentukan cabang olahraganya tersendiri seperti atletik. Untuk tunarungu ada yang berbeda. Kebutuhan kompetisi yang menentukan cabang yang dilatih, bukan hanya minat pribadi.

P7: Bagaimana reaksi siswa lain melihat teman yang menang atau berprestasi?

Jawaban: Siswa lain ikut semangat dan termotivasi: 'Saya mau ikut lomba seperti kakak, mau menang, mau dapat hadiah.' Guru juga memberikan reward, yang semakin mendorong semangat kelompok.

P8: Apakah ada peningkatan kemampuan fisik setelah mengikuti kegiatan olahraga?

Jawaban: Ya. Siswa tunagrahita juga bisa mengalami tantangan fisik – beberapa dulu sering jatuh meski berjalan di tempat yang datar. Setelah latihan fisik rutin, mereka menjadi lebih kuat, lebih stabil, dan akhirnya bisa berlari dengan percaya diri.

P9: Bagaimana cara mengukur peningkatan kemampuan fisik?

Jawaban: Terutama melalui observasi. Kami memperhatikan pergerakan, postur, dan daya tahan fisik mereka dari waktu ke waktu.

P10: *Bentuk penyesuaian apa yang diberikan saat latihan?*

Jawaban: Untuk siswa dengan kebugaran fisik lemah, kami berkonsultasi dengan guru olahraga untuk menyesuaikan kegiatan. Misalnya, siswa yang belum bisa berlari dengan baik akan mendapat latihan yang dimodifikasi sesuai kapasitas fisiknya.

P11: *Apakah aturan permainan dimodifikasi?*

Jawaban: Ya, harus dimodifikasi. Modifikasi olahraga di SLB bukan hanya diperbolehkan – itu adalah suatu keharusan dan terbukti efektif dalam memfasilitasi partisipasi siswa.

P12: *Bagaimana olahraga memengaruhi kepercayaan diri siswa?*

Jawaban: Olahraga berpengaruh besar pada kepercayaan diri. Siswa yang dulu takut tampil di depan orang lain menjadi terinspirasi ketika melihat temannya berhasil. Ketika guru berkata 'lompat ke depan' dan siswa melompat, mereka merasakan 'Saya juga bisa.' Olahraga memicu rasa pencapaian yang membangun kepercayaan diri.

P13: *Bagaimana interaksi sosial antara siswa disabilitas dan non-disabilitas?*

Jawaban: Ketika siswa dari kelas kami mengikuti lomba bersama siswa dari sekolah reguler, kemampuan sosial mereka juga meningkat. Mereka menjadi lebih komunikatif, berani bertanya kepada peserta lain tentang cabang lomba mereka.

P14: *Apakah program olahraga sudah menciptakan lingkungan yang inklusif?*

Jawaban: Di SLB, siswa sudah berbaur antar berbagai jenis ketunaan, yang sudah merupakan bentuk inklusi alami. Pemantauan inklusi eksternal biasanya ditangani oleh pimpinan sekolah (wakasek dan tim asesmen).

P15: *Apa kendala utama dalam menjalankan program olahraga?*

Jawaban: Setiap anak memiliki tantangan yang berbeda. Dalam satu kelas yang beranggotakan lima siswa, ada lima masalah yang berbeda. Beberapa orang tua tidak sejalan dengan guru, menganggap anaknya tidak boleh dipaksa. Selain itu, hanya ada satu guru olahraga untuk semua siswa SMP dan SMA – sangat menantang, meski semangat guru olahraganya membuat hal itu terasa lebih ringan.

P16: *Apakah fasilitas sudah memadai?*

Jawaban: Belum sepenuhnya. Sekolah berusaha menyediakan peralatan seperti papan keseimbangan, tapi jumlahnya tidak cukup untuk semua siswa. Kadang antar guru berebut sarana yang sudah ada namun belum tercukupi.

P17: *Apakah dukungan dari orang tua dan komunitas?*

Jawaban: Banyak keluarga yang ekonominya terbatas. Sebagian orang tua memberikan dukungan – ada yang menawarkan untuk mengantar atau menemani. Sangat bergantung pada situasi setiap keluarga masing-masing.

P18: *Apakah kekuatan utama program olahraga ini?*

Jawaban: Siswanya sendiri – banyak yang benar-benar berbakat. Dan guru-gurunya mau membantu memfasilitasi meski fasilitas tidak lengkap. Misalnya kalau tidak ada lapangan, kami meminjam lapangan di sebelah atau membawa siswa ke fasilitas UNP yang terdekat.

P19: *Apakah program ini akan terus berlanjut?*

Jawaban: Pasti berlanjut, karena perlombaan diadakan setiap tahun dan siswa yang berminat serta berbakat harus terus dikembangkan. Harapan saya adalah sarana-prasarana yang lebih baik dan kerjasama yang lebih erat dengan Dinas Olahraga, termasuk kunjungan pelatih dari dinas untuk membimbing teknik olahraga secara spesifik.

GURU – GILANG DWI NANDA

P1: Sudah berapa lama Bapak terlibat dalam program olahraga di sekolah ini?

Jawaban: Nama saya Gilang Dwi Nanda. Saya adalah guru seni budaya di SLBN 1 Padang, tetapi kami juga memiliki program ekstrakurikuler untuk pengembangan minat dan bakat siswa di bidang olahraga. Saya sudah mengajar di sini kurang lebih 12 tahun. Di luar sekolah, saya juga merupakan pengurus SOINA (Special Olympics Indonesia).

P2: Apa peran utama Bapak dalam program olahraga?

Jawaban: Sudah ada guru olahraga yang bertanggung jawab untuk pelatihan teknis. Para guru lain, termasuk saya, lebih banyak memantau perkembangan latihan siswa. Karena guru olahraga hanya satu, semua guru dilibatkan. Kami diajarkan teknik-teknik dasar dan peraturan lomba yang kemudian kami terapkan bersama siswa saat latihan.

P3: Bagaimana tingkat keterlibatan siswa dalam kegiatan olahraga?

Jawaban: Untuk siswa dengan hambatan intelektual, kemampuan kinestetik adalah yang paling perlu dikembangkan. Mereka umumnya bersemangat dalam olahraga – ini adalah salah satu cara terbaik untuk mengembangkan kemampuan motorik kasar mereka.

P4: Apa yang mempengaruhi semangat siswa untuk berpartisipasi?

Jawaban: Pertama, mereka tertarik pada olahraga yang mereka lihat dan sukai. Kedua, guru olahraga mengemas pelajaran dengan cara yang menyenangkan sejak awal, menggunakan media permainan sehingga olahraga tidak terasa monoton. Untuk atlet bocce misalnya, selalu ada variasi agar mereka tetap termotivasi. Singkatnya: variasi pembelajaran dan pendekatan guru yang efektif adalah kuncinya.

P5: Strategi apa yang digunakan untuk melibatkan semua siswa?

Jawaban: Belajar sambil bermain. Saya mencari aktivitas kreatif yang menarik – bahkan dari konten viral di TikTok – dan mencobanya bersama siswa. Olahraga tidak selalu harus tentang kompetisi. Kami bertujuan menjadikan aktivitas fisik sebagai rutinitas yang menyenangkan, bukan sekadar jalur meraih medali.

P6: Apakah ada perbedaan minat antara jenis disabilitas yang berbeda?

Jawaban: Ya. Anak-anak Down Syndrome cenderung menyukai bocce yang memang sesuai kemampuan mereka. Mereka juga suka berenang karena menyukai air. Anak-anak autisme cenderung kurang cocok dengan olahraga tim karena keterbatasan sosial mereka.

P7: Bagaimana reaksi siswa lain terhadap prestasi teman mereka?

Jawaban: Setiap siswa yang berprestasi di perlombaan mendapat penghargaannya kembali pada upacara hari Senin, disertai sertifikat dari sekolah. Pengakuan ini memotivasi siswa lain untuk juga ingin namanya dipanggil saat upacara.

P8: Apakah ada peningkatan kemampuan fisik setelah berpartisipasi dalam olahraga?

Jawaban: Ya. Ada satu siswa bernama Audia (yang kini telah meninggal akibat kecelakaan), yang menunjukkan peningkatan fisik luar biasa melalui terapi renang rutin. Renang mengurangi risiko kesehatannya dan meningkatkan kondisi fisiknya secara signifikan dari waktu ke waktu.

P9: *Bagaimana Bapak menilai peningkatan fisik siswa?*

Jawaban: Sebelumnya, beberapa siswa yang tampak mengantuk atau kurang fokus ternyata hanya karena kebugaran fisik yang rendah. Setelah rutin berolahraga, stamina dan daya tahan mereka meningkat, fokus bertambah, dan mereka lebih bersedia berpartisipasi dalam kegiatan kelompok seperti gotong royong.

P10: *Adaptasi apa yang diberikan saat latihan?*

Jawaban: Adaptasi kurikulum adalah standar bagi siswa berkebutuhan khusus. Untuk siswa tunarungu, isyarat visual menggantikan sinyal verbal. Untuk siswa tunagrahita, materi dan cara penyampaian disederhanakan. Untuk pengguna kursi roda, kegiatan berlari dimodifikasi menjadi balap kursi roda.

P11: *Seberapa efektif adaptasi tersebut?*

Jawaban: Kadang sangat efektif, kadang kurang. Tapi adaptasi selalu berdampak – meski besar kecilnya berbeda-beda. Yang paling penting adalah tidak menerapkan metode yang dirancang untuk anak normal kepada siswa berkebutuhan khusus, karena itu tidak akan berhasil.

P12: *Bagaimana olahraga membantu membangun kepercayaan diri siswa?*

Jawaban: Khalid adalah contoh yang baik. Ia pindah dari sekolah reguler karena sering dibully akibat lambat belajar. Ia kemudian balik mem-bully orang lain. Setelah diasesmen, ditemukan ia memiliki gangguan perilaku dan hambatan intelektual. Ia masuk ke sini dengan enggan. Ketika renang diidentifikasi sebagai kekuatannya dan ia diikuti lomba, ternyata ia menang. Sejak itu, kepercayaan dirinya di sekolah berubah total.

P13: *Bagaimana interaksi sosial siswa disabilitas dengan non-disabilitas?*

Jawaban: Khalid, dengan hambatan intelektual ringan, tidak tampak berbeda dari anak normal oleh orang luar. Ia sudah bisa membaca, berhitung, dan bersosialisasi dengan baik. Ketika kami pergi memberikan bantuan bencana, orang-orang terkejut melihatnya: 'Ini dari SLB?' Mereka tidak percaya.

P14: *Apa kendala utama yang dihadapi?*

Jawaban: Pertama, keterbatasan jumlah guru – semua harus dilibatkan dalam pendampingan ekstrakurikuler olahraga. Kedua, fasilitas yang masih kurang: tidak ada lapangan bocce khusus (kami memanfaatkan area belakang kelas), tidak ada lintasan lari memadai (kami membawa siswa ke UNP atau UNAN). Anggaran juga menjadi kendala – pengembangan olahraga yang berkualitas membutuhkan dana yang tidak sedikit.

P15: *Apa dukungan yang diberikan orang tua dan komunitas?*

Jawaban: Bervariasi. Orang tua Audia sangat mendukung – mereka mendaftarkan anaknya ke klub renang sehingga ia menjadi juara. Orang tua Khalid, meski disarankan hal yang sama, tidak mengikutinya karena perbedaan prioritas atau mindset. Sekitar 5% orang tua mendampingi siswa ke perlombaan.

P16: *Apa kekuatan utama program olahraga ini?*

Jawaban: Kini kami sudah memiliki guru penjaskes khusus – ini adalah kemajuan besar. Kami juga memiliki tim kerja (Timwok) yang solid dan budaya kolaborasi yang fleksibel antar guru. Kepala sekolah pun mendukung secara finansial semaksimal mungkin, terutama untuk perlombaan.

P17: *Apa yang perlu diperbaiki?*

Jawaban: Mencampurkan siswa yang benar-benar atletis dengan yang sekadar mengisi slot ekstrakurikuler menciptakan gangguan saat sesi latihan yang serius. Idealnya, atlet serius dilatih terpisah. Selain itu, penganggaran untuk latihan berkelanjutan – seperti membawa atlet renang ke kolam secara rutin – harus dimasukkan secara formal dalam anggaran sekolah.

P18: *Apakah program ini akan terus berlanjut?*

Jawaban: Pasti. Olahraga memberikan aktualisasi diri yang tidak bisa diperoleh siswa melalui akademik. Di bidang olahraga, seni, dan keterampilan, siswa kita bisa benar-benar bersaing. Olahraga juga mempromosikan gaya hidup sehat – nilai yang harus kita contohkan sebagai guru untuk diri kita sendiri terlebih dahulu.

GURU – LILIANA SARI

P1: Sudah berapa lama Ibu terlibat dalam program olahraga di sekolah ini?

Jawaban: Nama saya Liliana Sari, wali kelas di jenjang SDLB. Saya berkecimpung di pendidikan khusus sejak tahun 2010, sudah 16 tahun. Pengalaman pertama saya adalah mendampingi siswa Down Syndrome untuk lomba lari 50 meter putri tingkat nasional di ajang SOINA pada tahun 2010. Pengalaman itu semakin memperdalam kecintaan saya terhadap anak berkebutuhan khusus, terutama anak dengan hambatan intelektual dan Down Syndrome.

P2: Apa peran utama Ibu?

Jawaban: Saat lomba, saya berperan sebagai pelatih dan pendamping. Untuk siswa SDLB, pembelajaran PJOK jarang didampingi guru olahraga khusus, sehingga wali kelas menangani semua mata pelajaran termasuk olahraga, pendidikan agama, bahasa Indonesia, dan mata pelajaran umum lainnya. Ketika ada siswa berpotensi, kami ditunjuk sebagai pelatih dan pendamping untuk perlombaan.

P3: Bagaimana tingkat keterlibatan siswa dalam kegiatan olahraga?

Jawaban: Olahraga adalah kegiatan pengembangan diri yang penting bagi anak Down Syndrome. Mereka mengalami hambatan motorik kasar dan motorik halus, dan olahraga – bahkan yang sederhana di dalam kelas – adalah salah satu alat pengembangan yang paling efektif. Kegiatan seperti lempar tangkap bola melatih koordinasi mata-tangan dan kedekatan emosional antara guru dan murid.

P4: Apa yang mempengaruhi kemauan siswa untuk berpartisipasi?

Jawaban: Kepercayaan diri dibangun dari dalam kelas. Jika tidak dibangun di sana, akan sangat sulit menggerakkan mereka di lapangan. Kriteria utama adalah: apakah mereka mengerti instruksi? Yang bisa memahami perintah dan dapat dilatih diprioritaskan untuk dipilih, bukan berdasarkan usia atau lama sekolah. Kami juga membangun kemitraan dengan orang tua untuk memperkuat latihan di rumah.

P5: Strategi apa yang digunakan agar semua siswa aktif?

Jawaban: Untuk perlombaan, kami memilih kandidat terbaik. Namun di kelas, semua siswa dilatih sesuai tingkatannya. Ketika seorang anak menolak melakukan sesuatu – misalnya melempar bola bocce – kami menggunakan motivator: 'Setelah lempar bola, Ibu belikan jus, es krim.' Pendekatan yang disesuaikan dengan karakter anak sangat penting karena anak berkebutuhan khusus memerlukan strategi yang personal.

P6: Apakah ada perbedaan minat antara jenis disabilitas?

Jawaban: Ya, tapi potensi tidak selalu langsung terlihat. Guru perlu menstimulasi dan menemukan bakat yang tersembunyi. Kebutuhan perlombaan juga menentukan olahraga apa yang dilatihkan. Anak yang bakat alamiahnya sesuai kebutuhan kompetisi langsung teridentifikasi; yang lainnya membutuhkan lebih banyak stimulasi dan percobaan.

P7: Bagaimana reaksi siswa lain melihat teman yang aktif berolahraga?

Jawaban: Saat senam pagi hari Kamis, Anda bisa melihat jelas perbedaannya: ada yang hanya berdiri menonton, ada yang langsung bergerak ketika mendengar musik, ada yang butuh dorongan guru. Ketika anak yang semula diam melihat temannya bergerak, rasa ingin tahu perlahan menariknya untuk ikut. Guru yang berdiri di samping dan memberikan dorongan – 'Ayo, coba gerakkan tangan seperti ini' – adalah jembatannya.

P8: Apakah ada peningkatan kemampuan fisik setelah mengikuti olahraga?

Jawaban: Bahkan aktivitas kecil sekalipun memberikan hasil yang besar. Misalnya, meminta anak berjalan di atas kursi yang disusun berjejer (setinggi 20 cm) untuk melatih keseimbangan – tampak sepele bagi orang lain, tapi bagi siswa kita itu adalah tantangan yang signifikan. Setelah 4–5 kali pertemuan, anak yang tadinya sangat takut perlahan menjadi percaya diri. Latihan berulang adalah kuncinya – tidak ada kegiatan yang tidak bermanfaat bagi siswa berkebutuhan khusus.

P9: Bagaimana cara mengukur peningkatan fisik?

Jawaban: Melalui pengamatan pribadi. Karena setiap anak memiliki kebutuhan berbeda, penilaian bersifat individual – bisa dengan cross check atau deskriptif yang disampaikan kepada orang tua.

P10: Bentuk adaptasi apa yang digunakan?

Jawaban: Siswa yang belum bisa menggunakan papan titian melewati tahapan lebih sederhana: berjalan di garis dulu, kemudian di atas ubin, baru ke papan. Untuk bola: bola kecil terlebih dahulu sebelum bola besar. Setiap langkah di-scaffold berdasarkan kemampuan anak saat ini.

P11: Apakah aturan permainan dimodifikasi?

Jawaban: Ya. Dalam satu kelas bisa ada siswa dari kelas 2 hingga kelas 4 dengan level kognitif yang berbeda-beda. Permainan digunakan untuk mengajarkan keterampilan hidup sekaligus – antri, mengikuti aturan, kerjasama tim. Misalnya, permainan basket sederhana mengajarkan siswa cara berbaris, menunggu giliran, dan mundur ke belakang setelah giliran selesai.

P12: Seberapa efektif alat bantu yang disesuaikan?

Jawaban: Sangat efektif. Media yang bervariasi membuat siswa tetap terlibat. Ketika satu aktivitas membosankan mereka, beralih ke aktivitas lain menjaga sesi tetap berjalan. Beragam media Montessori di laci kelas diperkenalkan di awal tahun dan digunakan secara strategis sepanjang tahun.

P13: Bagaimana program olahraga mendukung kepercayaan diri siswa?

Jawaban: Sekolah menghargai siswa yang berprestasi, yang memotivasi teman-teman mereka. Kesempatan tidak hanya diberikan kepada pemenang, tetapi bergantian sesuai kemampuan. Ini menciptakan budaya di mana setiap siswa berpotensi untuk diakui.

P14: Bagaimana interaksi sosial antara siswa disabilitas dan non-disabilitas?

Jawaban: Siswa tunagrahita ringan dan tunarungu umumnya bersosialisasi tanpa kesulitan jika menemukan teman yang cocok. Siswa Down Syndrome membutuhkan lebih banyak bimbingan untuk berinteraksi, terutama dengan orang baru. Dengan dukungan dan keakraban, mereka bisa terhubung.

P15: Apa kendala utama yang dihadapi?

Jawaban: Menemukan bibit bakat sejak dini adalah tantangan terbesar. Ketika siswa berprestasi yang lebih tua lulus, atlet pengganti harus dicari dari siswa yang lebih muda yang potensinya belum tentu langsung terlihat. Mengidentifikasi siswa baru yang berpotensi di olahraga membutuhkan pengamatan yang cermat dan stimulasi yang kreatif.

P16: *Apa dukungan dari orang tua dan komunitas?*

Jawaban: Kolaborasi multi-pemangku kepentingan sangat penting: pemerintah, sekolah, guru, dan orang tua harus bekerja sama. Jika orang tua tidak mendukung kegiatan atau tidak bisa menemani anaknya yang butuh pendampingan, program tidak bisa berjalan dengan optimal. Organisasi seperti SOINA, PEPARDA, dan PETAMAS menyediakan wadah kompetisi yang memotivasi sekolah untuk melatih siswa dengan serius.

P17: *Apa kekuatan utama program ini?*

Jawaban: Sekolah khusus (SLB) berfokus pada kemandirian siswa, bukan akademik. Olahraga dan seni adalah saluran utama pembentukan kemandirian tersebut. Anak yang belum bisa membaca mungkin adalah atlet lari tingkat nasional dengan deretan piala di rumahnya. Setiap program saling melengkapi.

P18: *Apa yang perlu diperbaiki?*

Jawaban: Pertama, identifikasi bakat yang lebih terencana, bukan sekadar penugasan acak. Kedua, guru sebagai praktisi multi-peran harus meningkatkan kompetensi di cabang olahraga yang dipercayakan, bahkan jika itu berarti belajar dari awal. Membangun kepercayaan diri siswa juga krusial: banyak anak berkata 'Saya tidak bisa, saya tidak mau' padahal mereka jelas memiliki kemampuan.

P19: *Apakah program ini akan terus berlanjut?*

Jawaban: Ya, selama platform kompetitif masih ada. Keberadaan perlombaan memberikan makna pada latihan yang dilakukan di sekolah. Tanpa platform itu, potensi siswa akan tetap tersembunyi.

GURU – RINI AGUSTA

P1: *Sudah berapa lama Ibu terlibat dalam program olahraga di sekolah ini?*

Jawaban: Nama saya Rini Agusta. Saya mengajar di sini sejak tahun 1989, sudah 37 tahun. Saya akan pensiun bulan Agustus ini. Saya pernah mengajar siswa dengan berbagai jenis disabilitas: tunagrahita, Down Syndrome, dan remaja di tingkat SMA. Saya juga memegang tugas tambahan – sebelumnya sebagai Wakil Kepala Sekolah Bidang Kesiswaan, sekarang Bidang Kurikulum.

P2: *Apa peran utama Ibu?*

Jawaban: Sebagai wali kelas dan Wakasek Kurikulum, keterlibatan saya adalah dalam perencanaan dan pengawasan program ekstrakurikuler dan olahraga. Instruksi olahraga langsung dilakukan oleh guru bidang studi penjaskes (saat ini Bu Dea). Saya memberikan pengawasan dan arahan. Perencanaan program dilakukan oleh tim – guru olahraga menyusun program, tim berdiskusi, kemudian dipresentasikan kepada kepala sekolah.

P3: *Bagaimana tingkat keterlibatan siswa dalam olahraga?*

Jawaban: Setiap hari Kamis, siswa dan guru berolahraga bersama (senam). Ini merupakan bagian dari program olahraga. Ketika kelas lain sedang berolahraga di luar, siswa dari kelas lain pun ingin ikut bergabung – menunjukkan antusiasme yang nyata. Tunagrahita, tunarungu, dan berbagai jenis disabilitas lainnya semua berbaur dan bermain bersama dalam sepak bola, bulu tangkis, bocce, dan lompat jauh.

P4: *Apa yang mempengaruhi semangat siswa?*

Jawaban: Pertama, dorongan dari guru dan orang tua. Siswa perlu terus diberi motivasi dengan contoh nyata: 'Teman kamu rajin berlatih, menang piala, dan diumumkan di upacara. Apakah kamu juga mau seperti itu?' Memberikan insentif yang nyata dan terlihat – seperti melihat teman sebaya dihargai secara publik – mendorong motivasi.

P5: *Strategi apa yang digunakan agar semua siswa berpartisipasi?*

Jawaban: Kami memberikan isyarat motivasi yang konkret dan berulang. Kami berkata kepada siswa: 'Yang rajin dan berkelakuan baik dipilih; yang malas dan nakal tidak dipilih.' Mungkin siswa belum sepenuhnya memahami penalaran abstrak, tapi mereka merespons bahasa sebab-akibat yang jelas. Dorongan yang konsisten dan terus diinternalisasi perlahan mengubah perilaku mereka.

P6: *Apakah ada perbedaan minat partisipasi antar jenis disabilitas?*

Jawaban: Tidak terlalu berbeda – semangatnya sama saja. Mereka bermain bersama tanpa memandang jenis disabilitas. Mereka saling mengamati dan merespons satu sama lain. Satu-satunya perbedaan yang mereka sadari adalah ada teman yang 'tidak bisa bicara' (tunarungu), tapi mereka tidak mengonseptualisasikan 'kategori disabilitas.'

P7: *Bagaimana reaksi siswa lain ketika teman mereka menang?*

Jawaban: Mereka mengekspresikan kekaguman atau keinginan ringan: 'Teman kamu menang kemarin.' Ini sebenarnya sehat – menunjukkan mereka memiliki keinginan dan kesadaran. Guru menyalurkan perasaan itu menjadi motivasi konstruktif untuk event berikutnya.

P8: Apakah ada peningkatan kemampuan fisik?

Jawaban: Ya. Kita bisa melihat perbedaan fisik yang jelas antara siswa yang rutin berolahraga dengan yang tidak – dari fisik, kelincahan, dan koordinasi gerak. Untuk pemain bocce, peningkatan terlihat dari fokus dan presisi dalam menggelindingkan bola.

P9: Adaptasi apa yang diberikan?

Jawaban: Latihan disesuaikan dengan tingkat kemampuan setiap siswa. Peralatan dan tugas juga disesuaikan. Semuanya – dari alat hingga intensitas latihan – disesuaikan dengan kapasitas fisik dan kognitif siswa.

P10: Bagaimana olahraga membantu kepercayaan diri?

Jawaban: Siswa mendapat kepercayaan diri dengan bertemu teman-teman sebaya dari sekolah lain di event. Mereka bersosialisasi, berinteraksi, bahkan membuat teman baru. Menariknya, siswa itu sendiri sering terlihat tenang dan santai di perlombaan – justru guru pendampinglah yang paling tertekan! Siswa dengan Down Syndrome khususnya tampak tidak terpengaruh oleh tekanan kompetisi.

P11: Bagaimana interaksi sosial dengan non-disabilitas di event?

Jawaban: Perlombaan kami biasanya masih dalam komunitas disabilitas – belum terintegrasi dengan sekolah reguler di event. Di dalam sekolah sendiri, semua jenis disabilitas berbaur dengan bebas. Siswa dengan disabilitas fisik (tunadaksa) yang menggunakan kursi roda bahkan dibantu oleh teman-temannya tanpa diminta.

P12: Apa kendala utama yang dihadapi?

Jawaban: Tantangan utama adalah kolaborasi dengan orang tua. Kadang orang tua menyerahkan segalanya kepada sekolah. Tanpa upaya bersama antara sekolah dan keluarga, perkembangan siswa menjadi terbatas. Kami terus berupaya menjembatani kesenjangan itu melalui komunikasi dan dorongan yang berkelanjutan.

P13: Apakah fasilitas sudah memadai?

Jawaban: Alhamdulillah, sekolah cukup lengkap. Semua peralatan yang diperlukan tersedia.

P14: Apa kekuatan utama program ini?

Jawaban: Kerjasama tim di dalam sekolah – antara tim olahraga, tim kurikulum, dan pimpinan sekolah. Dikombinasikan dengan dukungan anggaran dan evaluasi program yang rutin, program ini berkelanjutan dan efektif.

P15: Apakah program ini akan terus berlanjut?

Jawaban: Ya. Program ekstrakurikuler olahraga direncanakan setiap tahun dan dievaluasi secara berkala. Ini bukan program sementara – sudah tertanam dalam kalender sekolah dan terus ditinjau untuk perbaikan.

GURU – ROSMADAWATI

P1: Sudah berapa lama Ibu terlibat dalam program olahraga di sekolah ini?

Jawaban: Di sekolah ini kurang lebih 2 tahun – saya pindah ke sini pada tahun 2023. Sebelumnya saya sudah pernah bekerja dengan siswa disabilitas di sekolah lain.

P2: Apa peran utama Ibu?

Jawaban: Untuk siswa yang akan berlomba, peran saya adalah melatih mereka dalam cabang yang akan dipertandingkan – mengajarkan teknik, menjelaskan peraturan lomba, dan memperjelas apa yang dinilai dalam perlombaan.

P3: Bagaimana tingkat keterlibatan siswa dalam olahraga?

Jawaban: Siswa tunagrahita memahami konsep perlombaan, berbeda dengan siswa jenis ketunaan lain yang mungkin belum memahaminya. Beberapa siswa berkata 'Saya tidak bisa, Bu' – dan tugas kami sebagai guru adalah menanamkan keyakinan: 'Kamu bisa, ayo latihan dulu.' Jika dibiarkan sendiri, mereka tidak akan mau tampil. Dorongan kami sangat penting.

P4: Apa yang mempengaruhi semangat siswa?

Jawaban: Motivasi dari guru adalah penggerak utama – kami membangun keyakinan diri mereka agar merasa mampu. Setelah kepercayaan diri batin itu terbentuk, mereka berani untuk mengikuti perlombaan.

P5: Apakah ada perbedaan minat partisipasi antar jenis disabilitas?

Jawaban: Bervariasi berdasarkan individu, bukan jenis disabilitas. Beberapa siswa tunagrahita memiliki kepercayaan diri tinggi dan antusias berlomba; yang lain lebih tertutup. Dibandingkan dengan jenis ketunaan lain, siswa tunagrahita memahami konsep menang dan kalah, sementara yang lain mungkin tidak – mereka berlari karena semua berlari, tanpa memahami konteks kompetitifnya.

P6: Bagaimana reaksi siswa lain ketika teman mereka aktif berolahraga?

Jawaban: Mereka pun menjadi semakin semangat – melihat teman yang aktif memotivasi yang lain untuk ikut.

P7: Apakah ada peningkatan kemampuan fisik?

Jawaban: Ya – siswa yang rutin berolahraga tampak lebih bugar secara fisik. Pelari, misalnya, menunjukkan kondisi fisik yang lebih baik dibandingkan sebelum berlatih.

P8: Bagaimana cara mengukur peningkatan fisik?

Jawaban: Dengan mengamati kekuatan, postur, dan ketahanan – siswa tampak lebih tegak, lebih kuat, dan lebih mampu dari waktu ke waktu.

P9: Adaptasi apa yang digunakan dalam latihan?

Jawaban: Latihan disesuaikan dengan kapasitas setiap siswa. Misalnya, jika siswa belum bisa berlari 200 meter, kami mulai dari 100 meter dan bertahap meningkatkannya.

P10: *Apakah aturan permainan dimodifikasi?*

Jawaban: Ya – baik dalam permainan maupun kegiatan kelas. Modifikasi dilakukan sesuai kebutuhan siswa. Misalnya, siswa yang perlu mengembangkan motorik halus diberi bola berduri untuk dipegang dan dipijat.

P11: *Seberapa efektif adaptasi yang dilakukan?*

Jawaban: Sangat bermanfaat. Ketika latihan dan alat disesuaikan dengan kebutuhan siswa, dampaknya jelas dan bermakna.

P12: *Bagaimana olahraga memengaruhi kepercayaan diri?*

Jawaban: Sebelum berlomba, siswa biasanya kurang percaya diri. Tapi begitu berada di lapangan – ketika melihat ada peserta yang kemampuannya di bawah mereka – kepercayaan diri mereka tumbuh. Setelah menang, antusiasme mereka berlipat ganda.

P13: *Bagaimana interaksi sosial dengan non-disabilitas?*

Jawaban: Untuk siswa tunagrahita, komunikasi dan sosialisasi umumnya tidak menjadi masalah. Mereka bisa berinteraksi dengan anak-anak non-disabilitas di luar sekolah. Setelah memenangkan perlombaan, mereka sering mendapat pujian dari teman-teman di lingkungan rumah, yang membuat mereka bangga.

P14: *Apa kendala utama yang dihadapi?*

Jawaban: Meyakinkan siswa untuk berpartisipasi adalah bagian yang paling sulit. Beberapa menolak di awal, dan guru terkadang harus mengunjungi rumah mereka hanya untuk membujuk mereka agar mau menghadiri perlombaan.

P15: *Apakah fasilitas sudah memadai?*

Jawaban: Ada yang sudah, ada yang belum. Misalnya, lapangan untuk lempar turbo terlalu sempit. Kami memanfaatkan ruang yang ada sekreatif mungkin.

P16: *Apa dukungan dari sekolah, orang tua, dan komunitas?*

Jawaban: Dukungan ada, meskipun terbatas. Ketika lapangan yang memadai tidak tersedia, kami menggunakan ruang yang ada secara kreatif.

P17: *Apa kekuatan utama program ini?*

Jawaban: Olahraga meningkatkan semangat siswa, memperbaiki kebugaran fisik, dan menyediakan saluran bagi bakat mereka. Bagi siswa tunagrahita yang IQ-nya lebih rendah, potensi mereka di bidang olahraga dapat sepenuhnya terwujud dan memberikan rasa pencapaian.

P18: *Apa yang perlu diperbaiki?*

Jawaban: Kami membutuhkan lebih banyak guru penjaskes khusus atau pelatih eksternal dengan keahlian mendalam di cabang olahraga yang diajarkan – terutama untuk event kompetitif seperti bulu tangkis. Wali kelas seperti kami memiliki pengetahuan umum tetapi mungkin tidak memiliki keahlian mendalam pada teknik olahraga tertentu.

P19: *Apakah program ini akan terus berlanjut?*

Jawaban: Ya – kini kami sudah memiliki guru penjaskes khusus, program ini lebih siap. Olahraga tidak hanya mendukung prestasi tetapi secara fundamental melayani kesehatan dan kesejahteraan siswa.

BAGIAN B: WAWANCARA ORANG TUA

ORANG TUA – GUSLINA

P1: *Boleh Ibu perkenalkan diri dan ceritakan tentang anak Ibu?*

Jawaban: Nama saya Lina. Saya orang tua dan wali kembar Zikra dan Zikri. Setelah diasesmen, mereka didiagnosis tunagrahita, keterlambatan bicara, dan kurang perhatian. Kini mereka berusia 16 tahun. Saat usia 7 tahun, mereka belum bisa bicara. Kami bawa ke Padang untuk terapi di RS Semen Padang – secara fisik normal, tetapi dirujuk ke sini untuk sekolah sekaligus terapi. Setelah 7 tahun, mereka sudah bisa bicara (meski masih ada cadelnya), membaca, berhitung, dan mengurus diri sendiri secara mandiri.

P2: *Sudah berapa lama anak-anak mengikuti program olahraga?*

Jawaban: Sudah 7 tahun di sekolah ini. Mereka mulai serius bermain sepak bola sekitar setahun belakangan. Untuk olahraga umum, mereka ikut setiap minggu pada hari olahraga yang dijadwalkan.

P3: *Apakah Ibu melihat ketertarikan mereka terhadap olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ya – mereka antusias. Mereka sering memakai baju bola ke sekolah di hari olahraga. Di rumah, mereka suka menonton pertandingan sepak bola di televisi.

P4: *Apakah mereka konsisten mengikuti latihan?*

Jawaban: Ya – setiap minggu mereka mengikuti jadwal olahraga tanpa harus diingatkan.

P5: *Apakah mereka perlu didorong untuk ikut?*

Jawaban: Tidak – mereka sudah tahu jadwal olahraga mereka dan menantikannya. Mereka saling mengingatkan satu sama lain: 'Besok hari olahraga, kita main bola.'

P6: *Apakah ada perubahan fisik setelah mengikuti olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ya – terlihat perkembangan fisik dan peningkatan kekuatan. Mereka tangguh – tidak peduli hujan atau panas. Mereka juga jarang sakit sekarang.

P7: *Apakah mereka lebih mandiri setelah mengikuti olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ya – setelah hari olahraga, mereka mencuci baju olahraga sendiri tanpa disuruh.

P8: *Apakah kepercayaan diri mereka meningkat?*

Jawaban: Ya – kepercayaan diri mereka sudah meningkat.

P9: *Bagaimana hubungan sosial mereka dengan teman-teman?*

Jawaban: Mereka selektif dalam memilih teman – tahu mana teman yang baik dan mana yang tidak. Mereka menjaga jarak dari yang suka mengolok-olok atau menipu mereka.

P10: *Apakah mereka tampak lebih bahagia dan bersemangat?*

Jawaban: Ya – mereka selalu excited dengan kegiatan berikutnya. Setelah pulang sekolah dan olahraga, mereka tidur nyenyak, jam 8 malam sudah tidur dan bangun segar di pagi hari.

P11: *Apakah kepercayaan diri berbicara di depan umum meningkat?*

Jawaban: Untuk berbicara di depan umum belum – mereka masih cenderung malu di keramaian. Itu masih perlu terus ditingkatkan.

P12: *Apakah mereka bercerita tentang teman baru dari kegiatan olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ya – terkadang mereka menyebutkan nama teman baru ketika pulang ke rumah.

P13: *Bagaimana pandangan Ibu tentang dukungan sekolah?*

Jawaban: Dukungannya lebih dari cukup. Alhamdulillah.

P14: *Bagaimana peran guru dan pelatih?*

Jawaban: Guru-guru fokus dan berdedikasi dalam mengajar anak-anak.

P15: *Apakah ada hambatan yang ditemui?*

Jawaban: Tidak ada – semuanya berjalan lancar dan menyenangkan bagi anak-anak.

P16: *Apa manfaat terbesar dari program olahraga?*

Jawaban: Setelah sekolah dan olahraga, mereka tidur dengan nyenyak dan bangun penuh semangat. Aktivitas memberikan struktur dan pengelolaan energi yang baik dalam keseharian mereka.

P17: *Apa yang perlu diperbaiki?*

Jawaban: Tidak ada yang besar – mereka menyukai sepak bola dan kegiatan yang ada sudah cukup memadai. Mungkin variasi seperti basket ketika mereka sudah siap.

ORANG TUA – HERLINA DEWIFERI

P1: *Boleh Ibu ceritakan tentang putra Ibu?*

Jawaban: Anak saya Fajri (Pajri), lahir tahun 2010 – kini 16 tahun. Bahkan sebelum sekolah pun ia sudah sangat aktif – pergi sendiri, jalan ke sungai mencari batu, aktif seharian. Biasanya ia tidak pulang sampai waktu Maghrib.

P2: *Sudah berapa lama ia mengikuti program olahraga?*

Jawaban: Fajri pindah dari SD 01 ke sekolah ini sekitar kelas 4 ke kelas 5 SD. Sekarang ia sudah SMA kelas 1 di sini.

P3: *Apa minat utamanya dalam olahraga?*

Jawaban: Hobinya adalah bulu tangkis. Ia sering mengikuti perlombaan dan sering menang. Di rumah sudah banyak pialanya.

P4: *Apakah ia konsisten dalam berlatih?*

Jawaban: Sangat konsisten – ketika ada perlombaan yang akan datang, ia berlatih dengan penuh semangat bersama guru-guru lain. Bahkan saat tidak ada lomba pun ia tetap semangat karena guru-guru mengingatkan: 'Fajri, nanti ada kesempatan lagi – terus latihan, pasti dipilih.'

P5: *Apakah minatnya terhadap olahraga berubah sejak bergabung di sekolah ini?*

Jawaban: Tetap fokus pada bulu tangkis, meski ia juga ikut olahraga lain yang tersedia. Semangat kompetitifnya kuat – ia berpartisipasi dalam berbagai perlombaan.

P6: *Apakah ia antusias mengikuti perlombaan dan latihan?*

Jawaban: Ya – sangat antusias. Semangat dan antusiasmenya terus tumbuh di setiap perlombaan yang diikuti.

P7: *Apakah ia perlu dorongan dari orang tua?*

Jawaban: Ia butuh dorongan dari dirinya sendiri sekaligus dari guru – keduanya berperan.

P8: *Apakah ia lebih aktif bergerak di rumah setelah olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ia tetap aktif baik di sekolah maupun di luar.

P9: *Apakah kesehatannya meningkat?*

Jawaban: Ya – ia jarang sakit, meski sering keluar dalam panas atau hujan, atau pergi ke sungai. Daya tahan fisiknya terbilang sangat kuat.

P10: *Apakah olahraga membuatnya lebih mandiri?*

Jawaban: Ya. Ketika tidak ada makanan di rumah, ia memasak mi sendiri. Ia mandiri dalam urusan sehari-hari.

P11: *Apakah kepercayaan dirinya meningkat?*

Jawaban: Sangat meningkat – ia tidak malu kepada siapa pun. Ia percaya diri dalam tampil dan mempresentasikan dirinya.

P12: *Bagaimana kehidupan sosialnya dengan teman sebaya?*

Jawaban: Ia bergaul baik dengan semua orang – tidak ada masalah di sekolah maupun di lingkungan rumah. Teman-teman datang ke rumah untuk menjemputnya.

P13: *Apakah ia tampak lebih bahagia dan bersemangat setelah olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ya – ia penuh energi dan bahagia. Piala dan penghargaan yang ia menangkan juga memberi rasa bangga dan kepuasan.

P14: *Apakah ia bercerita tentang teman baru dari perlombaan?*

Jawaban: Ya – ia bercerita tentang bertemu peserta dari sekolah lain. Ia menyebutkan bahwa kadang lawannya jauh lebih besar darinya, yang ia anggap lucu.

P15: *Bagaimana pandangan Ibu tentang dukungan sekolah?*

Jawaban: Dukungan sekolah sangat baik. Ia bisa berpartisipasi dalam berbagai jenis perlombaan berkat fasilitas dari sekolah.

P16: *Bagaimana peran guru dan pelatih?*

Jawaban: Mereka sangat baik – penuh pengertian dan terlibat. Mereka melatih siswa dengan penuh dedikasi.

P17: *Apa hambatan yang pernah ditemui?*

Jawaban: Tantangan terbesar di rumah adalah waktu belajar. Ibunya buta huruf, sehingga dukungan akademik di rumah sangat terbatas. Abangnya kadang membantu, tapi tidak konsisten.

P18: *Apa manfaat terbesar dari program ini?*

Jawaban: Olahraga membantu Fajri bertemu teman-teman dari sekolah lain dan memperluas jaringan sosialnya di luar komunitasnya yang langsung.

P19: *Apa yang perlu diperbaiki?*

Jawaban: Fajri mungkin agak lambat dalam beberapa hal, tetapi guru-guru lain memahami kecepatannya dan bekerja sesuai dengannya.

ORANG TUA – IKHSAN ENDRIZUL

P1: *Boleh Bapak ceritakan tentang putra Bapak?*

Jawaban: Anak saya berusia 17 tahun. Di rumah ia santai-santai saja dan sebagian besar main HP.

P2: *Bagaimana ia awalnya tertarik pada olahraga?*

Jawaban: Rumah kami dekat sungai, jadi sejak kecil ia sudah berenang di sana secara alami. Paparan awal itulah yang akhirnya membawanya ke renang kompetitif.

P3: *Apakah ia konsisten dalam berlatih?*

Jawaban: Ia sudah rutin berenang di sungai sejak kecil – lebih ke kebiasaan alami daripada latihan terstruktur.

P4: *Apakah ada perubahan motivasi terhadap olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ia tetap fokus pada renang dan lari – minatnya tidak bergeser ke cabang olahraga lain.

P5: *Apakah ia antusias menunggu jadwal latihan?*

Jawaban: Ia cukup santai soal itu – tidak terlalu excited, tapi mau ikut.

P6: *Apakah ia butuh dorongan dari orang tua untuk berlatih?*

Jawaban: Tidak – ia ikut atas keinginannya sendiri.

P7: *Apakah kondisinya meningkat?*

Jawaban: Ya – ada peningkatan yang cukup baik.

P8: *Apakah ia sering sakit?*

Jawaban: Tidak – ia jarang sakit.

P9: *Apakah ia lebih aktif di rumah?*

Jawaban: Tingkat aktivitasnya di rumah kurang lebih sama seperti sebelumnya.

P10: *Apakah ia menjadi lebih mandiri?*

Jawaban: Ya – ada peningkatan dalam kemandiriannya.

P11: *Apakah kepercayaan dirinya meningkat?*

Jawaban: Ya – ia semakin percaya diri dalam tampil dan mempresentasikan dirinya.

P12: *Bagaimana hubungan sosialnya dengan teman sebaya?*

Jawaban: Ia cenderung di rumah dan kurang berkomunikasi dengan teman di luar – tapi ada beberapa interaksi sosial yang tetap terjalin.

P13: *Apakah ia tampak lebih bahagia dan bersemangat secara keseluruhan?*

Jawaban: Ya – ia lebih bersemangat, terutama setelah menang.

P14: *Apakah ia lebih berani berbicara?*

Jawaban: Di keramaian, ia cenderung diam. Ia mengekspresikan emosi secara pribadi – bahagia atau marah tergantung apakah ia terganggu atau tidak.

P15: *Apakah ia bercerita tentang teman baru dari event?*

Jawaban: Ya – ia menyebutkan bertemu anak-anak dari sekolah lain di perlombaan.

P16: *Sudah berapa kali ia menang?*

Jawaban: Sekitar 3–4 kali.

ORANG TUA – JUSNIWATI

P1: *Boleh Ibu perkenalkan diri dan ceritakan tentang anak Ibu?*

Jawaban: Anak saya berusia 15–16 tahun dengan disabilitas tunagrahita. Komunikasinya agak lambat – ia mengerti hal-hal tetapi memprosesnya lebih perlahan.

P2: *Sudah berapa lama anak Ibu mengikuti program olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ia mengikuti olahraga di sekolah – program berdasarkan di sana.

P3: *Apakah Ibu melihat minatnya terhadap olahraga?*

Jawaban: Tidak terlalu terlihat di rumah – ia cenderung lebih banyak di dalam rumah. Sesekali ia jogging di lingkungan bersama teman-teman.

P4: *Apakah ia menyukai kegiatan olahraga sekolah?*

Jawaban: Ia ikut penjaskes di sekolah, dan sesekali jogging di kampung.

P5: *Apa yang memotivasi minatnya dalam olahraga?*

Jawaban: Sulit ditentukan – tampaknya lebih situasional, didorong oleh konteks sekolah.

P6: *Apakah ia bercerita tentang sekolah atau olahraga di rumah?*

Jawaban: Tidak terlalu – ia jarang berbagi detail tentang kesehariannya.

P7: *Apakah ia menjadi lebih kuat secara fisik setelah olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ya – secara fisik ia tampak lebih kuat.

P8: *Apakah ia sering sakit?*

Jawaban: Ia kadang sakit, tapi tidak parah – tidak ada demam, biasanya hanya ketidaknyamanan ringan.

P9: *Apakah ia menjadi lebih mandiri?*

Jawaban: Saya rasa ada sedikit kemandirian, meski saya tidak selalu di rumah untuk mengamatinya.

P10: *Apakah kepercayaan dirinya meningkat?*

Jawaban: Tidak banyak perubahan terlihat di rumah – ia mendapat pujian dan dorongan di sekolah, tapi tampaknya tidak terlalu terbawa ke perilaku di rumah.

P11: *Bagaimana hubungannya sosialnya di lingkungan rumah?*

Jawaban: Ia bermain dengan anak-anak di lingkungan rumah – baik laki-laki maupun perempuan, termasuk teman-teman yang sudah SMA.

P12: *Apakah ia bercerita tentang teman baru dari olahraga?*

Jawaban: Tidak – ia jarang berbagi detail seperti itu.

P13: *Bagaimana pandangan Ibu tentang dukungan sekolah?*

Jawaban: Saya kurang tahu detail sepenuhnya – saya sering bekerja ketika ia di rumah. Saya tidak mengetahui semua aktivitas sekolahnya secara rinci.

P14: Apakah Ibu pernah mendampingi ke perlombaan?

Jawaban: Tidak – saya mempercayakannya kepada guru dan pelatih.

P15: Apa hambatan dalam kegiatan olahraga?

Jawaban: Di rumah tidak ada fasilitas olahraga – olahraga hanya terjadi di sekolah.

P16: Apa manfaat terbesarnya?

Jawaban: Ia lebih aktif melalui lingkungan sekolah – program yang terstruktur membuatnya tetap terlibat.

ORANG TUA – ELI YARNI

P1: *Boleh Ibu ceritakan tentang putra Ibu?*

Jawaban: Putra saya Rio berusia 15 tahun dengan disabilitas tunagrahita. Di rumah ia kebanyakan bermain di dalam, karena teman-teman di lingkungan kebanyakan anak normal dan ia pernah dibully – jadi ia jarang keluar rumah kecuali untuk sholat di masjid.

P2: *Sudah berapa lama Rio mengikuti program olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ia sudah 7 tahun di sekolah ini, dengan olahraga setiap hari Kamis.

P3: *Apakah Ibu melihat minat Rio terhadap olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ya – ia tampak menyukai sepak bola, tapi di tingkat SD, olahraga di sekolah masih bersifat umum dan belum terspesialisasi.

P4: *Apakah Rio antusias dengan olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ketika lelah, ia menjadi kurang semangat. Tapi umumnya, ketika bersama teman-teman, ia bahagia dan aktif.

P5: *Apakah ia butuh dorongan untuk ikut?*

Jawaban: Ya – terkadang perlu sedikit dorongan, terutama ketika ia kelelahan.

P6: *Apakah kondisinya meningkat setelah olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ya – terlihat ia punya lebih banyak energi. Ia juga lebih sehat – jarang sakit sejak rutin berolahraga.

P7: *Apakah olahraga membuatnya lebih mandiri?*

Jawaban: Ia lebih banyak bicara – berbagi apa yang ia pelajari di sekolah dengan ayahnya di rumah.

P8: *Apakah kepercayaan dirinya meningkat?*

Jawaban: Ya – mulai ada, meski masih perlu terus dikembangkan. Di tingkat SD, olahraga belum terspesialisasi, sehingga pembangunan kepercayaan diri yang lebih fokus melalui olahraga kemungkinan baru akan datang di tingkat SMP.

P9: *Bagaimana hubungan sosialnya?*

Jawaban: Di sekolah ia punya teman; di rumah lebih sedikit karena riwayat bullying tadi.

P10: *Apakah ia tampak lebih bahagia secara keseluruhan?*

Jawaban: Ya – ia bahagia melakukan aktivitas fisik. Ia tampak gembira saat berlari-larian.

P11: *Bagaimana dukungan sekolah?*

Jawaban: Ia butuh kehadiran orang tua atau sosok yang dikenal – ketika saya terlambat datang di salah satu event olahraga, ia menolak masuk. Ia membutuhkan rasa aman dan kehadiran seseorang.

P12: *Apa kendala utamanya?*

Jawaban: Ia kurang fokus tanpa pendamping. Ia butuh pelatih atau guru yang konsisten hadir dan berfokus padanya.

P13: *Apa manfaat terbesar dari program olahraga?*

Jawaban: Pergi ke sekolah memberinya motivasi – ia bersemangat ketika ada kegiatan. Ketika guru sebelumnya sempat absen dan kemudian kembali, ia langsung menunjukkan antusiasme yang nyata.

P14: *Apa yang perlu diperbaiki?*

Jawaban: Kemampuannya untuk fokus secara mandiri. Ia butuh pendamping yang konsisten dan berdedikasi untuk membantu membangun kemandirian dan konsentrasinya dalam olahraga.

ORANG TUA – MUNIARTI

P1: *Boleh Ibu ceritakan tentang putra Ibu?*

Jawaban: Nama anak saya Khalid (Kholit). Ia berusia 18 tahun. Kehadiran sekolahnya tidak menentu – kadang pergi, kadang tidak.

P2: *Sudah berapa lama ia mengikuti program olahraga?*

Jawaban: Dari kelas 2 SMP sampai sekarang SMA kelas 1.

P3: *Apa prestasi olahraganya?*

Jawaban: Ia mencoba renang saat SMP – dan tiba-tiba meraih juara dua. Guru-gurunya bilang ia punya bakat nyata di renang.

P4: *Apakah ia konsisten dalam berlatih?*

Jawaban: Latihan di kolam renang sekolah ada, tapi akses kolam yang konsisten masih terbatas.

P5: *Apakah motivasinya berubah sejak ikut olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ya – ia lebih termotivasi untuk datang ke sekolah ketika ada kegiatan olahraga.

P6: *Apakah ia menunggu jadwal latihan dengan semangat?*

Jawaban: Ia antusias pada hari olahraga (hari Jumat).

P7: *Apakah ia butuh dorongan untuk ikut?*

Jawaban: Ya – ada dorongan sedikit dari saya yang diperlukan.

P8: *Apakah kondisinya fisiknya meningkat?*

Jawaban: Daya tahan fisiknya meningkat – ia lebih tangguh.

P9: *Apakah ia lebih aktif di rumah?*

Jawaban: Ya – ia sedikit lebih aktif.

P10: *Apakah ia menjadi lebih mandiri?*

Jawaban: Ya – ia menunjukkan kemandirian yang lebih besar dalam kegiatan sehari-hari.

P11: *Apakah kepercayaan dirinya meningkat?*

Jawaban: Ya – kepercayaan dirinya tumbuh melalui partisipasi olahraga.

P12: *Bagaimana hubungan sosialnya di lingkungan rumah?*

Jawaban: Ia bermain dengan anak-anak di sekitar rumah, termasuk permainan tradisional. Ia cukup aktif secara sosial di lingkungan sekitar.

P13: *Apakah ia bercerita tentang kegiatan sekolah di rumah?*

Jawaban: Ya – ia menceritakan tentang menanam sayuran dan kegiatan sekolah lainnya.

P14: *Apakah ia bercerita tentang teman baru dari perlombaan?*

Jawaban: Ia excited dengan event yang akan datang – terutama renang. Untuk lari ia juara dua, tapi untuk renang ia jauh lebih bersemangat.

P15: *Apakah Ibu mendampingi ke perlombaan?*

Jawaban: Tidak – saya menyerahkan kepada guru dan pelatihnya. Latihan dilakukan sepenuhnya di sekolah.

P16: *Apa manfaat program olahraga?*

Jawaban: Memberikan motivasi dan struktur baginya. Ia menantikan kegiatan dan suasana hatinya serta keterlibatannya secara keseluruhan meningkat di hari-hari olahraga.

ORANG TUA – RENI SURYANI

P1: *Boleh Ibu ceritakan tentang putra Ibu, Imam?*

Jawaban: Imam adalah remaja dengan disabilitas tunagrahita. Kehidupan sehari-harinya normal – ia aktif dan ikut kegiatan komunitas seperti Posyandu Remaja.

P2: *Sudah berapa lama ia mengikuti olahraga?*

Jawaban: Sejak SD.

P3: *Apakah ia sering ikut perlombaan?*

Jawaban: Ya – ia sudah banyak ikut perlombaan dan sudah menang.

P4: *Mengapa Imam lebih tertarik pada olahraga daripada akademik?*

Jawaban: Ia secara alami lebih condong ke aktivitas fisik daripada pelajaran teori. IQ-nya di bawah rata-rata untuk mata pelajaran akademik, tapi di bidang olahraga ia unggul.

P5: *Apakah ia butuh dorongan untuk ikut olahraga?*

Jawaban: Tidak – ini keinginannya sendiri. Saya hanya mengikuti dan mendukungnya.

P6: *Apakah kondisinya meningkat?*

Jawaban: Ya – daya tahan fisiknya meningkat sejak aktif berolahraga.

P7: *Apakah ia membantu di rumah?*

Jawaban: Tidak banyak dalam hal pekerjaan rumah tangga.

P8: *Sudah berapa kali ia menang?*

Jawaban: Sudah banyak kali di berbagai cabang olahraga – termasuk lompat tinggi. Ia ikut banyak event.

P9: *Apakah ia tampak lebih bahagia setelah olahraga?*

Jawaban: Ia selalu bahagia – olahraga menjaga semangatnya. Ia juga ikut randai (seni pertunjukan tradisional), yang berkontribusi pada kemampuan berekspresinya.

P10: *Apakah kepercayaan dirinya dalam berekspresi meningkat?*

Jawaban: Ya – ikut randai membuatnya lebih nyaman tampil dan berekspresi di depan orang lain.

P11: *Bagaimana pandangan Ibu tentang dukungan sekolah?*

Jawaban: Dukungan sekolah sangat baik.

P12: *Apakah Ibu mendampingi ke perlombaan?*

Jawaban: Ya – saya pergi untuk melihat ia tampil.

P13: *Apakah orang tua lain menunjukkan apresiasi terhadap prestasi Imam?*

Jawaban: Orang tua lain di sekolah memperhatikan dan menghargai prestasi-prestasinya.

P14: *Apakah Ibu akan merekomendasikan sekolah ini kepada orang lain yang berkebutuhan khusus?*

Jawaban: Ya – saya kenal orang yang awalnya ragu tentang SLB, tapi setelah melihat lingkungan dan hasilnya, mereka akhirnya menghargainya.

P15: *Apakah ada bullying di sekolah atau lingkungan rumah?*

Jawaban: Tidak ada bullying – tidak di sekolah, tidak pula di lingkungan rumah.